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VOL. 4 NO. 02 (2024): RJAI

1. BUKHARA TRADITIONAL JEWELRY
Koryogdi Dzhuraevich Dzhumaev, Viloyat Rajabovna Tuksanova
1-7
2. FERTILITY OF IRRIGATED SOILS AND ITS MODULATION
Mahfuza Muhiddinovna Sattorova
8-14
3. CATEGORIES OF TIME AND ASPECT IN GERMAN (The Categories of Tense and Aspect)
F. B. Mattiyeva, A. Rustamov
15-18
4. GRAMMAR CATEGORIES IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES
N. S. Normurodova
19-24
5. MAINTAINING A RENTAL ACCOUNT IN ACCORDANCE WITH INTERNATIONAL STANDARDS OF FINANCIAL REPORTING IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN
A. M. Babadjanov, Sh. M. Baymetova
25-39
6. MANAGING CONFLICTS IN VULNERABILITY AND PATCH MANAGEMENT FOR IT AND OT
Robert Kemp, Richard Smith
40-62
7. EFFECTS OF CRUDE OIL CONTAMINATION ON ATTERBERG LIMITS OF SELECTED SOIL ON THE SOUTH WEST KIRKUK-NE IRAQ
Burkan saeed Othman
63-70
8. IN CATTLE – A METHOD OF TREATING NODULAR DERMATITIS
Kasimov Sayfiddin, Begimkulova Yulduzoy
71-75
9. PEDAGOGY OF TEACHING IN NATIONAL MUSICAL ART
Ro'zimatov Asrorbek
77-82
10. CHARACTERISTICS OF RESPECT FOR ADULTS IN ELEMENTARY SCHOOL STUDENTS
Esemuratova Turganbike Aytmuratovna
82-86
11. SKILLS OF CREATIVITY IN MAKING DOLLS
Abdullayeva Ozodaxon
88-93

BUKHARA TRADITIONAL JEWELRY

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Summary

The article discusses the history of the development of art. In modern Uzbekistan, there are many architectural monuments, where there are examples of art. At the exhibition "Bukhara jewelry art" of the Art Museum named after Kamoliddin Behzod land.

Key words: Shell, bone, horn, forehead, ornament, earrings, decoration, "Shabaka".

Introduction

The roots of Uzbek jewelry go back to the distant past. Jewelry art has been preserved from the 6th to the 3rd millennium BC to the present day (Stone Age). Archaeologists - archaeologists found primitive female jewelry when opening ancient tombs. Beads and amulets made of stone, pottery, shells, bones, and horns are examples of jewelry from this period. Later bronze foreheads - amulets, hairpins, beads and other ornaments, as well as ornaments made of various stones - ornaments - testify to the ornaments of the Bronze Age.

Bukhara jewelry has been found during archaeological excavations in the Zeravshan oasis over the past 70 years in Zamon-bobod and Kuyi-Mazar.

The archaeological department of the Bukhara State Museum-Reserve presents artifacts of this period (III-II millennium BC).

At the exhibition "Bukhara jewelry art" of the Art Museum named after Kamoliddin Behzod land. Gold items found in the tomb of the Lower Tomb II - I centuries. AD: - women's jewelry; A button for elegant and women's clothing is displayed in the opening part of the exhibition.

Skillfully polished stone, studded with tourmaline, is sandwiched between gold wires and plates, and its conical shape attracts with its unique beauty. In particular, the skillful processing of gold made the jewelry unique. The balance of form and content shows the height of jewelry art. The button chased with gold is one of the most unique monuments of Central Asia, dating back to the second century BC. These artifacts indicate that the Bukhara school of jewelry art has been refined and improved over the centuries and has reached its high artistic image. These findings were discovered in 1952-1953 by the archaeologist O.V. Found in the grave of a rich woman Obelchenko.

By the 19th century, many types of jewelry in various styles were created in Bukhara.

By this time, the profession of a jeweler was divided among various professionals. In particular, master decorators - painters and engravers - created a very high level of appearance of products and enriched the Bukhara school of jewelry art. Master jewelers are mainly made from silver, less often from gold, as well as the original metal with precious shiny stones such as rubies, emeralds, sapphires: semi-precious, matte, opaque, but transparent, such as duralumin, turquoise, onyx, ruby, jade, coral, and with dark-colored stones and bones, as well as a wide range of colors that have become widespread since the second half of the nineteenth century. Zebi is a jeweler who makes jewelry, depending on the type of product, it is called tapishsoz, gulibotsoz, uzuksoz, hoop, etc.

Traditional metalworking techniques, which have long been popular with local jewelers, include a variety of carving, engraving, carving, embroidery, stepping, weaving. Masters also possessed the art of giving golden water, that is, gilding, stepping, blackening and grafting.

Each jewelry center has its own shape, raw materials, patterns and workmanship. Master jewelers have created simple, intricate pieces of jewelry such as rings, bangles, necklaces, and other intricately embroidered pieces that require great skill.

Variety of processing - decorations for women's clothing of various shapes are very elegant.

They adorn women's heads, forehead, nose, ears, hair, neck, chest, shoulders, waist, wrists and fingers. In the first days of marriage, young people put on all the bisot jewelry when they came to visit, on holidays, on holidays, by invitation, when a guest came. The rest of the time, women wore simple jewelry such as bangles, rings, and bangles.

Men's clothing also belonged to jewelry: a brooch on the groom's turban, a ring with his name, a belt with precious metal and stones, embroidered with a pattern, a knife with a handle, daggers and swords, sticks and even a saddle for rich men. The harness is also skillfully decorated by jewelers.

Making gold jewelry required more responsibility from jewelers, as the precious metal was faced with the task of creating art that would suit it. Basically, Bukhara gold was of high quality and had 750 samples. In the bisota of Bukhara jewelers of the 19th century, there are many jewelry techniques, including hoiskori - filigree and simtor "Shabaka". On the other hand, the Bukhara masters are also distinguished by the fact that they mastered these aspects at a high level.

Designed in the style of Shabaka, the gold base draws attention with its latticed look.

Another type of jewelry is katmola, made of gold and rubies. "Bozbandcha" in it is skillfully executed in the style of simtora. The divine power of the tumor to protect it from all sorts of evil eyes served to increase the power of faith entrusted to these "boz gangs". Many of them have a sheet of paper with verses from the Koran. Some of the amulets are filled with mastic and verses from the Quran or the words "Allah", "Bismillah" and "Muhammad" are printed on the surface in beautiful patterns. Other amulets also served as beautiful decorations, without any inscriptions.

Among women's jewelry, breast cancer has a special beauty - "a find is a tongue". Hoiskori in the shape of a heart is a symmetrical piece of jewelry embroidered with sapphires in three places.

The most popular types of jewelry rings that give beauty to women are "holak", "barg", "muhammadi", "shibirma", made by Bukhara jewelers. They are made of gold 750 in the style of print, wire, winding, riser, step, and also made of rubies and pearls. Depending on the number of rubies in Shibirma, it is called "yak quirota" or "du quirota".

Sometimes jewelry of the "kundalzozi" ring style is also found in the works of Bukhara jewelers.

Such rings are also called "panchpoya". The main part of the ring is suspended by three long legs and two rows of short legs between them.

They are made of coral and silver linen or rubies, emeralds and gold linen. Sometimes in silver and gold. The fact that the hoop is attached to a wire laid horizontally below the center of the circle, without bases, is called a "muhammadi

hoop" with an admixture of 1 large and two small rubies and emeralds on each side.

Among women's jewelry, jewelry worn on the forehead, temples and hair has a special look. The most common of them are "mohi-tillo" or "bibishak". These crescent shaped ornaments are basically made up of 3 identical sets. The lower part is decorated with 8 to 16 pearl or pearl legs, the main part of which is printed and filled with mastic. The "golden pipes" hanging in front of the two ears are also called zulf or gayjak. Because a bunch of women's hair is passed through them and tied with a silk thread.

The tubular cylindrical shape is decorated with a row of turquoise stones in three places in the form of a step, and a necklace hangs down from the bottom of the necklace. An almond-shaped "gajak" is attached to the ear and serves as a decoration. They are made of silver, with a row of pearl sprigs on one side of the almond-shaped surface covered with steps, and two rows of silver wires twisted together to pass over the top of the ear to form a rope.

Bukhara ornaments worn on the forehead are called "tilla bargak" and "bолоobro". They are 15 square plates arranged in a straight line, connected by turquoise and coral sapphires with two rows of plates at the bottom. The upper slots had two notches for easier access to the upper frets, the lower slots had two notches for easier access to the upper frets, and the lower slots had two notches for easier access to the upper frets.

The necklace worn by young brides is called hapaband. It looks like a gold leaf. It is also called hapaband because it sticks to the neck. The rings presented in the museum are made of silver and gold, some of them are decorated with precious stones, diamonds, emeralds and rubies.

At the beginning of the 20 th century, there were more than 400 jewelers in Bukhara, more than 50 of whom were engaged in creative search and reached the level of real jewelers, and the rest were created by other masters, copying forms and making products. Twenty of them became the owners of the palace, making objects for the palace in a special place in the state of Arkoni, "the highest bird." Their highest creation was presented to the emir. Samples from the confiscated property of the Emir of Bukhara, such as jewelry, gilded, embroidered and enameled silver suns, handkerchiefs, tulips, bowls, albums and chests are worthy of the museum's exposition. In the basement of the palace, in a special showcase, orders and medals of the Bukhara emirs, made by jewelers - coin acceptors, are exhibited. Sweets, glasses, wine and candles prepared for the palace were made

by master Tursinjon, master Mukhtorjon, master Sadriddin Pochcho, master Kasymjon, master Noman, master Mir Fuzeil, Lazgi Caucasian master Kasimjon Mirakov and master Kapaev.

Among the jewelers of Bukhara of the 19 th century, the most famous are the masters of rings, bracelets, zebigardon and other jewelry, masters Yodgor Haji, Mirzo Fozil, masters of pottery, master Kamolliddin, master Nasriddin, master Kordsharif, jeweler Nabi.

The work of Bukhara jewelers stands out as a unique school of Uzbek jewelry art due to the perfection of form, harmony of form and content, appropriateness and proportionality of jewelry to the product, harmony of selected colors and content. The simple and meticulous variety of artifacts formed in antiquity retains more valuable artistic features, which suggests that these items still exist among the people and that the high demand for them is not accidental.

From century to century, the disappearance of the same themes in jewelry and the emergence of other varieties, new interpretations of traditional elements, changes in the way of life of the people. But the centuries-old traditions, with their vitality, have become an art for life.

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FERTILITY OF IRRIGATED SOILS AND ITS MODULATION

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Annotation

This article provides information on the application of fertility parameters based on maintaining stability and the ecological state of the biolayer - the top soil layer, which is the main means of agricultural production, as well as on the basis of natural and climatic conditions and determining the level of soil fertility.

Keywords: Earth, soil, fertility, humus, microflora, biota, agricultural technology, model, agricultural climate, bioecology.

Introduction

Land and its soil resources in the Republic of Uzbekistan are the backbone of all existing industries, the main means of production. So, the development of the agricultural sector of our economy depends on it. Efficient use of various soils on irrigated lands plays an important role in the development of modern agriculture. Prospective agronomists, soil scientists, agrochemists and farm managers should study in detail the soils of the farm or individual area where they operate, as well as know the secrets of applying soil fertility measures. [1.204.]

The problems of soil fertility and its complete redevelopment have attracted the attention of researchers and scientists in recent years. In the concept of soil fertility in irrigated agriculture, it is necessary to add a number of other properties of the soil that ensure the growth and development of plants, such as soil air, physical and chemical properties, and so on. Soil fertility is manifested through its chemical, physical, physicochemical, biological properties. These additions were made as a result of an in-depth study of the soil requirements of cultivated plants. It should be noted that the productivity of agricultural crops is not entirely related to soil fertility, but also to the climatic conditions of the area, agro-technical measures, as well as the characteristics of the cultivars grown, and so on. The role of soil fertility factors in the irrigation process increases somewhat. This is because water and nutrient regimes allow a number of factors to be controlled to a certain extent, such as the plants going through certain stages during the growing season. [2.112-113] Soil organic matter is a key indicator that distinguishes it from soil-

forming rocks. Humus plays a major role as a “constituent” of the soil system. Of course, humus and soil fertility should not be equated with the amount of humus in the soil and productivity, but in any case, humus is to some extent a "storehouse" of plant nutrients - nitrogen, phosphorus, potassium and microelements. In addition, it contains enzymes, vitamins, growth substances. Perhaps this is why mineral fertilizers are better absorbed in well-drained humus soils. Soil fertility is determined not only by the total amount of humus in it, but also by the active humus in the top layer of the soil, which is renewed annually as a result of the decay of plant residues.

The environmental role of humus is also very large. Its effect on plant growth and development in a positive physiological-biochemical way is scientifically based. However, no matter how important humus is for soil fertility, the process of humus formation in general, like the process of soil formation, develops very slowly. [2.114.] The importance of soil physical properties in the fertility of irrigated soils is enormous. At a certain density of the soil, the development of the plant root system is improved, creating favorable conditions for the mineralization of plant residues. The conditions for the development of beneficial aerobic microflora (azotobacteria, etc.) in air-exchange soils are normalized, and the pathogenic effect of wilt-forming fungi and other disease-causing microorganisms is reduced. The soil density indicator shows the physical condition of the soil to a certain extent. If we take humus as the “Organizer” of the entire soil system, the Soil Density represents the general physical state of the entire soil mass. The process of irrigation, usually the density of the soil, indicates the physical state. This is due to the fact that the peculiar lyossimon, i.e. clay substances, interfere with the lower parts of the soil profile. In addition, the mechanical pressure of tractors and agricultural implements leaves a strong mark on soils that are wet and have a lot of moisture under the influence of irrigation. The soil seems to be tightly compacted under their weight. Degradation of soil mass also occurs during irrigation. In this regard, the density of soils is slightly higher than a certain level and is around 1.4-1.5 g / cm³ instead of 1.2-1.3 g / cm³. The physical condition of soils is one of the indicators that their density is somewhat controlled when the components of the farming network are applied correctly. This should be decided by choosing the time of tillage and tillage at a certain humidity, taking into account the local conditions, climate and soil characteristics of each place. [2.117.] In order to protect the fertility of irrigated soils and increase the productivity of agricultural crops, we recommend the following measures:

1. In dry years, it is possible to carry out spring wet irrigation, periodic leveling, economical use of irrigation water.
2. In order to increase soil fertility, it is expedient to introduce crop rotation and establish reserve trees.
3. In order to increase the efficiency of fertilizers, composting organic fertilizers with mineral fertilizers, feeding agricultural crops, applying 25-30 tons of organic fertilizers per hectare are highly effective.
4. Ensuring soil fertility and crop nutrients using cover crops
5. The use of cover crops in increasing the porosity and water absorption capacity of the soil
6. Periodic cleaning of collector drainage systems on farms, which increase their efficiency and prevent the rise of groundwater. When grouping soils according to the degree of salinity, attention is paid to the total amount of water-soluble salts and chlorine in them. With increasing salinity, soil quality deteriorates, fertility decreases, and reclamation measures become necessary.

Before sowing in saline soils, it is necessary to carry out the following reclamation measures:

- One of the most important measures to prevent soil salinization is the careful development of water use plans on the basis of rules that fully meet the requirements of agronomy, the transition to a new irrigation system, construction of hydraulic structures from irrigation stations, water conservation, pollution;
- It is possible to remove and improve the salinity of salts and salts of different levels by stopping the continuous rise of groundwater saline through the capillary pathways and removing harmful salts accumulated in the soil;
- To improve the physical and chemical properties of soils, it is necessary to put gypsum on these soils. Its feature is that it removes sodium and calcium from the absorbing complex of the soil, as well as improves the physical condition of the soil;
- Measures such as fertilization of loamy and loamy soils, deep plowing of loamy soils, large-scale introduction of irrigation works, digging ditches and reducing their level are the main measures to improve the physical and chemical properties of soil, increase its fertility. If agromeliorative measures are applied in a timely and correct manner, it is possible to plant crops in these soils and obtain consistently high yields from them; Salinity will increase further if the norm of saline leaching water is not taken into account when soil salinity is washed away, the depth and salinity of groundwater. Proper rotation improves the reclamation of saline and swampy soils, increases soil fertility and increases productivity. The reclamation effect of

crop rotation is that the soil is fertile, which increases organic and nutrient content, improves physical properties, and moisture evaporates less. [5.157.] Soil fertility is strongly related to genetic-geographical conditions, i.e., factors that shape soil types, the nature of the parent rock, the environment of the soil formation, and the characteristics that determine its use in agriculture. In irrigated soils, a significant portion of high, often excessive, mineral fertilizers are transferred to the lower part of the soil by irrigation water and accumulate there. They also pass into groundwater. As a result, they are polluted with nitrogen, phosphorus and their accompanying elements. This, in turn, worsens the overall environmental condition of the biocomplex. The productive capacity of soils is related to a number of factors that are not related to soil quality in addition to soil fertility. One of the most important of these factors is the agroclimatic factor. If the climatic conditions differ from the norm in one way or another, the harvest in that year will not be at the norm. In addition, the cultivated plant varieties are related to the state of beneficial and harmful organisms in the agro-system. None of these components should be considered. For example, no matter how fertile the soil is, no matter how good the biota is in it, if the land is not planted with a variety suitable for the soil and climatic conditions, the harvest will be almost non-existent. Thus, the above data index and characteristics are a parameter of productivity. They are created by taking them into account and modeling their interactions. [2.120.]

Many scholars give different meanings to the concept of model. In our opinion, the model is the standard. As for soil fertility, it is the sum of its specific properties, a function that maintains and increases soil fertility, ensuring a stable yield of agricultural crops. In other words, ensuring the yield of agricultural crops is a set of all the conditions necessary for the passage of certain soil regimes. The first generation of the soil fertility model is based on expert and statistical data in terms of agronomic soil science. They represent the total sum of agronomically significant properties and characteristics that determine the yield of agrosystems in a particular form. The simplicity of such models, their intelligibility to a wide range of specialists, the relatively small number of parameters, serve as a good basis for their subsequent research and development. In addition, they also blend well with farm soil maps and help apply them to agricultural production. These models are, as mentioned above, “first generation models” and reflect the state of some parameters of soil fertility, but do not fully reveal the dynamic relationship between them. In the study on modeling the fertility of irrigated soils, 2 class

models were distinguished. The first is a specific fertility model, which reflects the factors that make up soil fertility, including agronomic practices and climatic conditions. The second real fertility model is that it shows the current state of soil fertility. Comparing these shows which parameters of the soil differ to a certain degree. Such models allow to determine the level of soil fertility, determining the direction of agrotechnical and other measures. In addition, we show the fertility model of irrigated grassland soils:

Table - 1 Fertility model of irrigated meadow soils

Agronomic indicators		Models	
Agroclimate		Specific	Real
1.	Average annual rainfall, mm	300-320	266-440
2.	Average annual temperature	14,5	14,0-15,5
3.	Sum of effective t0 above 100s	2300	2140-2220
4.	Precipitation in March-Juneil, mm	100-120	100-200
5.	Water mode type	irrigation	avtomorph
6.	Irrigation rate, m3	4700	8000
Chemical		Specific	Real
1.	The amount of humus in the driving layer,%	1,5-2,0	1,3-2,2
2.	The amount of humus in the half-meter layer (average%)	0,09-0,11	1,2-1,70
3.	Total nitrogen,%	0,09-0,11	0,07-0,11
4.	Total phosphorus,%	0,18-0,20	0,15-0,18
5.	Total potassium,%	2,0	1,6-2,4
6.	Harakatchan phosphorus, mg / kg	30-45	20-140
7.	Motile potassium, mg / kg	300-400	200-500
8.	The sum of the absorbed cations	14-15	12-16
9.	At the rate of mg / eq per 100g of soil absorbed calcium,%	80	50-80
Agrophysical		Specific	Real
1.	Depth of driving layer, cm	30	28-35
2.	Physical lost amount,%	35-55	
3.	Density of driving layer, g / cm3	1,30 -1,40	
4.	Water permeability in 1 hour, mm.	70-90	
Bioecological			
Nitrogen utilization rate of plants Soil nitrification activity The amount of useful protofauna The amount of soil contaminants Contamination of soils with nitrogen phosphorus and others.			

Scientific research to further increase the fertility of irrigated soils and to develop ways to use them properly in agriculture has yielded certain results. However, it should be noted that the fertile potential of the oasis soils is not fully used to date. The main reason for this is that the factors that make up soil fertility have not been fully studied, and the factors that determine fertility have not been identified. The solution to these problems can be solved by creating their fertility models for each soil type.

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CATEGORIES OF TIME AND ASPECT IN GERMAN (The Categories of Tense and Aspect)

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Abstract

This article discusses the classification of word groups in modern German and Uzbek, primary grammatical categories, the division of existing words in each specific language into specific groups, lexical and lexical-grammatical, morphological forms in terms of their relevance to words belonging to a particular group.

Keywords: development, laws, worldview, aspirations, thinking, genres, personalities, fraternal tribes, during the reign, tribal languages.

Introduction

The tense category indicates the time of occurrence of the action understood from the verb. There are three grammatical tense forms in English: Present Tense, Past Tense, and Future Tense. Each of these tenses is made in its own way. The present tense form indicates that the action is related to the time at which the speech is spoken. "My brother studies in the second course. Now he is at home."

The modern form is used in a very broad sense. Modern forms of the verb can be used differently in different styles. For example: aphoristic present in proverbs, parables, and wise words of the present tense, gnomic present tense, generic time to express a general truth or reality, historical tense in narrating an action that occurred in the past tense, (Historical present) form is used. The past tense form indicates whether the action occurred before the time the speech was spoken.

Past tense forms of correct verbs in modern English are formed using -ed, while incorrect verbs are formed by changing the vowels in the stem or by other means. Past tense forms of verbs also form different groups according to their meanings. In modern English, the past tense form has three main forms:

- a) Indefinite past tense;
- b) Past perfect form;
- c) Future in the Past.

Each of these tense forms is used in two different aspects: common and continuous.

The next tense form represents that an action or process will occur after the time the speech is being uttered. In English, the future tense is formed by adding leading verbs in the infinitive form to the auxiliary verbs shall and will. In this case, the first person shall be used in singular and plural shall. Shall, a verb combination formed using will, is called an analytic form because shall, will added to the leading verb loses its lexical meaning and is used only as an indicator of grammatical tense. That is why the shall (will) infinitive analytic form is a simple cut in the sentence: "Well", said the stgapper, "I'll come but no handcuffs" (H. I. Wells).

The aspect category is related to the time category, more precisely to the time category. Verbs vary in both the tense category and the aspect category. Aspect refers to the nature of the occurrence of an action in verbs, i.e., the beginning, continuation, completion, and repetition of an action. Verbs in English are studied in two different aspects: a) Common Aspect and b) Continuous Aspect.

The general aspect provides general information about whether or not an action has occurred. In the continuous aspect, however, it indicates that the action is continuing at a certain time. The general aspect is definite and the continuous aspect is definite. The continuous aspect is formed by adding the adjective form I of the independent verb to any form of the auxiliary verb to be. For example:

to read — to be reading

He reads - He is reading

(She reads - She reads)

He read —He was reading

(He read - He was reading)

He will read - He will be reacting.

(He reads— He reads).

The use of the Present Tense of the Common Aspect. Modern forms are mainly used in the following cases:

a) when expressing a repetitive action:

He works from nine to five, rides the commuter special plants. His garden, makes love to his wife (B. J. Friedman): I go there once a month. In summer we sleep outdoors.

b) in the expression of the action that takes place in the present tense, that is, during the speech:

"I'm afraid I don't quite understand the "of course", answered March laughing (K. Chesterton).

c) is used to express the general truth, reality. This constant is called the present tense (generic present, gnomic present). For example:

To err is human (Proverb).

"Pagn Pago is the rainiest place in the Pacific."

g) used aphoristically in proverbs and sayings:

Still waters run deep. The deep river flows calmly (the bottom of the calm flowing water is deep).

A bird in the bush is worth two in the bush.

One bird in hand is better than two in a tree (a straw near a distant wheat is better, or a lung near a distant tail is better).

Where there is smoke there is a fire. Where there is smoke, there will be fire.

d) to express an action that belongs to the next tense in sentences following the tense and the condition.

If you make one wrong step, Swarts, you will get more trouble than is good for any living man (P. Abrahams). I'll come if he invites me. You'll get it when you come here. I'll send him a letter as soon as I get there.

e) To express an action that will take place in the near future. In such cases, the verbs to come, to go, to arrive, to start, to leave, etc. are used almost always:

My brother arrives in two days. My brother (or sister) will come in two days.

«Tomorrow, Sophie», she said dramatically, «we start for Rome, Tomorrow morning» (A. Huxley).

f) Instead of the past tense form, the present tense form can be used to narrate a past event more vividly: such a form is called a Dramatic (historical) Present.

I look over the rail. There, just below me, stand three young, it is too big to be called lads, each with a document like on Income Tax return in his hatband, and each with his arm affectionally round his neighbors neck, singing with all his

might. They are a little drunk, but not so drunk as German would be in like circumstances on German liquor. They are determined for in the highest spirits: I try to catch the words of their song, and just manage to make out the general sense of it ... (B. Shaw).

j) The writer describes an event and uses it as an appeal to students:

Who loves the haunts of Nature?
Love the sunshine of the meadow,
Love the shadow of the forest,
Love the wind among the boughs,
And the rain — shower and the snowstorm,
And the rushing of great rivers
Through their palisades of pine-trees
And the thunder in the mountains.

Verbs that are rarely used in the continuous aspect to see, to hear, to understand, to perceive, and other verbs are now used in the general aspect.

You see, son, you are the first child that has gone away from Stillefeld and became an educated man ... (P. Abrahams). You see why everyone is preparing, son (Ibid)

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GRAMMAR CATEGORIES IN ENGLISH AND UZBEK LANGUAGES

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Abstract

This article discusses the classification of word groups in modern English and Uzbek, primary grammatical categories, the division of existing words in each specific language into specific groups, lexical and lexical-grammatical, morphological forms according to their meanings to the generality of words belonging to a particular group.

Keywords: development, laws, worldview, aspirations, thinking, genres, figures, fraternal tribes, during the reign, tribal languages.

Introduction

Primary grammatical categories are word groups or lexical-grammatical groups of words. The words available in each specific language are divided into specific groups, which are called word groups. The classification of word groups in modern English and Uzbek is determined by the following characteristics of words, a) lexical and lexico-grammatical meanings, b) the generality of morphological forms for words belonging to a particular group, c) the role of words in speech. Word groups are also called lexical-grammatical categories of words because their lexical and grammatical forms are taken into account when dividing words into groups [Chomsky 1957: 416]. For example, all words in the horse category refer to the subject name. It should be noted, however, that not all horses need to be subject. Although some words do not denote an object, they are still used in place of an object. For example, love in English, place of joy, friendship in Uzbek, happiness and so on. Words belonging to the category of adjectives mainly represent the sign and feature of the object. For example: blue blue, white white, clever smart, in Uzbek: long, wide, active, etc. Words belonging to the category of verbs denote an action, state or process: run run, sleep sleep in Uzbek: to come, to blush, to see, and so on.

Each category has its own morphological forms of words, which form morphological paradigms and are associated with known grammatical categories.

For example, the suffix -s added to a horse in English means a category of numbers, and the suffix -ed in a verb means a category of time. The Uzbek language also has its own form of morphological paradigm, verbs and other word groups. For example: book - books; work - worked.

In addition, the words in each word group also perform a specific syntactic function in the sentence. For example: a noun can be mainly as a possessive, a complement, a predicative part of a participle, an adjective, a predicative part of a participle, a verb can be a participle of a sentence. Two or more word combinations can perform the same function in a sentence. For example, a horse can come as a determinant, as a number.

The communication process takes place with the direct participation of all language tiers. Even when a single tier is linguistically analyzed, the tiers are interconnected. For example, morphological tier units have their full description only in syntax. In modern English, a single word can refer to several word groups at the same time.

This is especially evident in the modern English noun and verb, as the reduction results in the disappearance of the distinctive characters at the end of the English noun and verb. It is very difficult to determine whether a word belongs to a lexical-grammatical word group. Words in modern English are not rich in morphological features. Therefore, the form of a word group may not differ from the second word group when it comes to its initial form or the first form of its paradigm. For example, if we take the words water, telephone, measure, mistake, they are both nouns and verbs at the same time, that is, water - water, to put water, to irrigate; telephone, to make a telephone call; measure - «measure, measure; mistake error; can come in the sense of making a mistake. Such cases are relative between horse and quality 1) relative; 2) related, relative; wet between adjective and verb 1) wet; 2) soaking, moistening; one between a horse and a stalk 1) a; something is an object, the person also encounters it regularly [Shaumyan 1965: 56].

Some are made in the presence of conversion, some are made as a result of the loss of flexion, and the amount of such common words that are compatible in terms of form is very large.

These include the following words: button - button, to button button, button, button, butter, to butter, butt swim, head hit, to butt swim, head hit, love love, to love, and so on.

Although the form is similar in modern Uzbek, many words belonging to different categories can be found at the same time. For example: finally 1) konets (horse); 2) nakonets (introduction), ignorant. 1) neprosveshennsh, tёмnyy (quality); - 2) glupets (ot); indefinite 1) netochnyy (quality); 2) neyasno (ravish).

As can be seen from the above examples, it is difficult to distinguish which category a word belongs to when taken separately in both English and Uzbek. In such cases it is necessary to use grammatical indicators. For example, in English and Uzbek, a noun can be distinguished from a plural morpheme. Compare: english-s, uzbek-s, girl girl, girlsgirls, master-masters, masters masters (masters), Uzbek: boy rich, children boys, working boy workers workers.

However, the plural morpheme does not always serve as a determinant. This is due to the presence of homonymous suffixes in nouns and verbs, not only in English and Uzbek, but also in many other languages. For example, in English the -s morpheme can make both the plural of the noun and the 3rd person singular of the verb: counts — 1) calculations, 2) he counts, counterfeits — 1) actions, 2) falsification.

In modern Uzbek, the suffix ham-lar can form the plural form of a noun and the conditional tense form of a verb. It should be noted that this condition is peculiar to verbs derived from the horse. For example, heads — 1) plural from the head, 2) perhaps those heads: branches — 1) branches of a tree, 2) branches (a tree produces horns), the English word for branches can also be given in this sense. In the examples shown, the root of both the horse and the verb are common, i.e., the verbs are made of horses.

Examples show that inflections, when taken separately, do not always fully reveal the nature of the noun and the verb. Therefore, the syntactic tier plays a decisive role in this. Compare: he eyes he looks, feel eyes his eyes, English: black eyes, he eyes (was). As can be seen from the English and Uzbek examples, the English eye word and the Uzbek eye word are neutral to lexical-grammatical categories of words. In both English and Uzbek, the same form comes in the form of a noun or a verb. They can only be distinguished syntactically.

Comparative grammar also contributes to the creation of bilingual dictionaries. The lexicographer must simultaneously describe the lexical and grammatical characteristics of the words included in the dictionary in both languages. Some of the word groups may have all three of the features mentioned above, and some may not be used as an independent part of speech in a sentence, although they do have lexical meaning and morphological form. In this regard, word groups are

divided into two parts: 1) independent parts of speech (Notional parts of speech), 2) auxiliary parts of speech (Structural parts of speech or function words).

Words belonging to independent word groups express lexically independent meanings, naming objects without the help of other words, indicating their quantity, sign, degree of fulfillment, the speaker's relation to the content of his speech. Independent word groups have paradigmatic forms that are grammatically related to certain grammatical categories and can perform a specific function in a sentence.

The next tense form represents that an action or process will occur after the time the speech is spoken. In English, the future tense is formed by adding leading verbs in the infinitive form to the auxiliary verbs shall and will. In this case, the first person shall be used in singular and plural shall. Shall, a verb combination formed using will, is called an analytic form because shall, will added to the leading verb loses its lexical meaning and is used only as an indicator of grammatical tense. That is why the analytic form shall (will) be a simple cut in the sentence: "Well", said the stgapper, "I'll come but no handcuffs" (H. I. Wells).

The aspect category is related to the time category, more precisely to the time category. Verbs vary in both the tense category and the aspect category.

Aspect refers to the nature of the occurrence of an action in verbs, i.e., the beginning, continuation, completion, and repetition of an action. Verbs in English are studied in two different aspects: a) Common Aspect and b) Continuous Aspect. The general aspect provides general information about whether or not an action has occurred. In the continuous aspect, however, it indicates that the action is continuing at a certain time.

The general aspect is definite and the continuous aspect is definite. The continuous aspect is formed by adding the adjective I form of the independent verb to any form of the auxiliary verb to be. For example:

to read — to be reading
 He reads - He is reading
 (She reads - She reads)
 He read —He was reading
 (He read - He was reading)
 He will read - He will be reacting.
 (He reads— He reads).

The Present Tense:

We begin the consideration of the tense category of verbs with indicative forms.

The time category is studied in the following order:

The present tense

The Present Tense

Non Perfect Perfect

Perfect

General aspect Common Aspect Continuous aspect

Continuous

Aspect General aspect

Common

Aspect Continuous aspect

Continuous

Aspect

Non-perfect present tense (NonPerfect Present Tense). The present perfect form of the verb consists of two opposite aspects:

1. Common Aspect

2. Continuous Aspect

The present tense in general.(The Present Tense of the Common Aspect). The present tense form in the general aspect of the verb is made up of the omitted infinitive. Only the third person singular form - (e) s suffix is added. For example:

I come he comes

We come she comes

You come It comes they come

This they rather enjoy: indeed, they finish it quite successfully (B. Shaw). With soothed nerves, they talk a little, drink a little, then began a little (Ibid). Then I understand the papers in their hatbands. (Ibid). She understands it well (Dreiser).

- When the suffix (e) s is added, the following changes occur in the structure of verbs:

a) If the verb ends with the letter -y and is preceded by a consonant, the letter -u becomes -i. For example:

fly - flies defy - defies

If the letter -y comes after the vowel, no change occurs

betray - betrays pay - pays

lay - lays employ - employs

b) If the end of the word ends with the vowel -o, -es is added.

go - goes, woo - wooes

embargo — embargoes

echo - echoes

c) -s is added after the -ee diagram.

see - sees flee - flees

r) In words ending in -e, s is added and the letter e is not pronounced:

pile - piles write— writes puzzle - puzzles

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MAINTAINING A RENTAL ACCOUNT IN ACCORDANCE WITH INTERNATIONAL STANDARDS OF FINANCIAL REPORTING IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract

In this article, it is considered that the issue of maintaining the rental account in accordance with international standards is expedient and it is necessary to support the state regulation of international standards of financial reporting. But, it was noted that rental accounting in the Republic of Uzbekistan has not developed for several reasons.

In the accounting account of the organizations of the Republic of Uzbekistan, the leased property is reflected as the amount of expenses under the lease contract, as well as other expenses related to the bringing of the property to a workable condition. In accordance with the IFRS (IAS) 17 "Rent" the lessee takes into account the asset received in the financial lease at the lowest of the fair value of the property or at the discounted value of the minimum rental payments. Enable users of the information to make management decisions about the facility with the most accurate assessment of the condition of the financial statements and to have a complete picture of the development of the organization. Conclusions and definitions regulating the accounting of rental relations in accordance with the normative documents of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the international standards of the financial reporting are given.

Keywords: Network, research, account policy, accounting, rental, leasing, international standards of financial accounting, tenant, development, analysis.

Introduction

In our country, in the modern conditions of the development of the market economy, rental relations have developed significantly. In order to carry out entrepreneurial activities, most economic entities that need modernized means of production, and in order to acquire them, it is necessary to withdraw large sums of money at the same time. Temporary obstacles to the process of implementation of the right to property become, specific features of the right to rent, in addition to, it can also be eliminated due to the rental relationship, which has become a complex of economic relations with financial rent.

The study is concerned with the need to create a unified accounting system and prepare financial statements for the participants of the rental relationship in the global economy of the country and the rapidly developing domestic market conditions for global integration and rental services. Such a system becomes the international standard of financial accounting. The formation of the financial account of the organization in accordance with the requirements of international standards remains an urgent task, in which it is impossible to effectively manage assets and passives, successfully carry out the process of attracting debt or capital funds.

International accounting system and accounting of account international standards (AAIS) play an important role in the development. AAIS serves as an important tool for the development of cooperation between countries, including economic relations and is an improvement of the investment climate in countries. That is why it is increasingly common in developed and developing countries, globally recognizing international standards by day, and designed to shift to the international standards of financial reporting.

This is stated in the resolution of the president of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated February 24, 2020 "on additional measures for the transition to International Financial Reporting Standards" PP-4611.

“In order to provide foreign investors with the necessary information environment and to expand their access to the international financial markets, as well as to improve the system of training specialists in the field of accounting and auditing in accordance with international standards by accelerating the transition to the international standards of financial reporting (IFRS):

Until the end of 2021, within the framework of international certification of accountants, a document on the successful submission of the science of "financial reporting on IFRS" or "Certified International professional Accountant (CIPA)", "Certified diploma accountant (CDA)", "Certified Public Accountant (CRA)" and "Diploma in international financial reporting (DipIFR)" to provide employees of the Accounting Service sufficient for the qualitative application of the international standards of financial reporting in the amount of at least three specialists with one of the certificates (in subsequent places - the International Accounting Certificate).

Critical analysis of the process of reforming the accounting system in the Republic from the point of view of the methods of changing the national standards of accounting led to the study of the world experience. The process of convergence of national standards to the international standards of financial accounting-the maximum convergence in the world, has shown that the method of gradual bringing of national standards in line with the international standards of financial accounting is Insolvency.

Differences in the procedure for accounting and presentation of reports of rental operations identified in the process of analyzing the local accounting system with the requirements of international standards impede the development of rental relations in the Republic and contribute to its instability and vulnerability, which is of particular importance in scientific research.

Materials

In the study of rental relations, it is of great importance to determine their types and classification criteria. At the same time, the classification of rent meets certain criteria. In this regard, within the framework of scientific research on the accounting of rental relations, it is necessary to analyze the basic international and local approaches to the classification of accounting rental types, taking into account the basic concepts that come with rental contracts. The analysis of the approaches to the classification of rental types makes it possible to understand the essence of the therefore it is determined by the technique of accounting for one or more types of rental transactions. In terms of classification of rental types, the problem of identification exists in both domestic and foreign theory and practice.

The reason for this can be different cases: the absence of a single opinion in determining the types of rents; the absence of a clear system in the selection of classification criteria, etc. The most important thing in the conclusion of a lease contract is the classification of the type of lease, tied to the organizational and legal form of the rental relationship. This classification also determines the order of calculations that performed by the participants of the lease agreement.

In accordance with international practice, a financial lease is an important transition to give the tenant all the risks and benefits associated with owning the asset, regardless of the transfer of the property to the tenant at the end of the lease term. In this case, the tenant granted the same rights and obligations as the payment received from the same person in the process of financial leasing of the property.

Financial lease agreement refers to the transfer of the object to the user, that is, the entire or almost all resource transferred to the tenant, it takes economic advantage in the process of resource use in the process of using the asset.

If the object purchased by the tenant rented to several tenants, as well as if the tenant should use this object for their own needs, then the current lease considered valid.

Given the classification of rent in international financial reports, we faced with some concepts and definitions that do not understand the essence of the class, the characteristics and terms of the rental relationship seem complicated. The terminology of the international standards of financial accounting in many respects resembles the terms used in the accounting of our country.

Economic service life is the economic benefit expected from the use of an asset by one or more users, or the number of units of products that obtained by one or more users. In this regard, the terms used in internal accounting are consistent with the international standards of financial accounting.

Useful service life – this is the period that has remained since the beginning of the lease, not limited to the period of its validity, during which time the organization assumes the economic benefits included in the asset. The term of use refers to the condition expected by the tenant, although the term of economic service refers to the asset. Thus, the useful life can be longer than the term of the lease, but not more than the term of economic service.

Rental period – this is the period when the tenant rents the property in accordance with the lease agreement, as well as the additional periods during which the lease agreement must be paid in addition or without additional payment, this is the time of the beginning of the term, since the tenant is in other words. This asset, liabilities, as well, the date of the initial recognition of income and expenses associated with the assignment of the lease term is.

Modern realities of the development of rental relations are becoming more and more common. Today, the majority of business entities must modernize their means of production in order to carry out their entrepreneurial activities, this they must simultaneously withdraw large sums of money from circulation. The difficulties that arise during the withdrawal of funds overcome due to the rental relationship. They have such a feature as financial rent that is, leasing. The relevance of the study of this topic has arisen from the fact that the integration of the global economy into the world, as well as the creation of a single accounting system in the conditions of the rapidly developing domestic market of rental services, and the need to prepare accounting financial statements for the participants of the rental relationship. Such a system can be IFRS (international standards of financial accounting).

In our opinion, if the property that is subject to leasing is under construction by the organization, the date of the conclusion of the financial lease agreement or the date of occurrence of the obligation has not yet been acquired, the date of the beginning of the next lease is the date of construction. This should have reflected in the account policy.

Method of Accounting for Rental Transactions

Unlike from the local account, the Accountant does not pay enough attention to the issues of accounting and accounting of the international standards of reporting, therefore, keeping records of economic operations in accounting is the private work of organizations. The trends of the latter lead to the fact that reporting is increasingly moving from accountants to professional users, therefore, it is no accident to recognize the international standards of accounting, which were previously recognized.

(IAS) has amended to international standards of financial reporting. Thus, the international standard of financial reporting, the formation of new account rules, increasing the level of accounting profession.

The procedure for accounting for rental relationship according to international financial reporting standards (IAS) 17 based on the international standards of the basic financial report analyzed during the study.

International financial reporting standards (IAS) 17 applies to all non-leased rent agreements, mainly related to the extraction or use of minerals, oil, natural and similar resources, in accordance with the "Rent"; license agreements for levies, patents and copyright.

International financial reporting standards (IAS) 17 "Rent" should not be used in the evaluation: financial rent terms and leases of investment property by the rent of the owners of the investment property for the purpose of rent. In this case, IFRS (IAS) 40 "investment property" is used. In addition, the methods of valuation are not applied to biological assets that provided for by the standard (IAS) 17 by tenants and landowners that are leased on a financial lease or operating lease (IAS) 41 "agriculture".

One of the main differences between the rules of internal accounting and the rules of IFRS (IAS) 17 is, first of all, the initial recognition of assets and rent obligations, as well as the subsequent reflection of income and expenses. The main purpose of forming a report is to provide information about the financial position of the organization at any time, that is, the actual value of its assets and liabilities. For this purpose, when the rent classified as Financial, the asset of the tenant's balance sheet reflected in the asset that leased as the main instrument and part of the obligation, but the future rent payments are in equal amounts.

In order to substantiate the need to reflect the financial rent agreement on the asset that leased, but on the balance sheet of the lessor, the following provisions can be implemented:

- It provides a reliable idea of the economic potential of the company, the material and technical capabilities of the accumulation of income;
- A more realistic picture of the level of financial dependence of a leasing company by external suppliers of financial resources, landlords and creditors appears.

Indeed, the company that has entered into a financial rent agreement for a long time will limit the use of income.

Thus, the leased asset is reflected in the balance sheet of the tenant the basis of the economic content of the transaction and the legal form of the transaction. The lack of property rights is stated in the financial statements.

At the same time, the asset corresponds to the balance sheet of the lessee to the account of the obligations in the amount equal to the minimum of the following assessments: at the fair value of the leased property or at the discounted value of the minimum rental payments, if it is lower than the fair value.

The report on profit and loss reflects the expenditure on interest, the report on cash flow-the payment of interest in the composition of cash flows from operating activities and the payment of rent debts in the composition of cash flows from financial activities.

The obligations of the tenant account under the international standards of a financial statement are assessed the amount of the minimum rental payments, they are combined in the form of credit elements: principal interest. Thus, each of the lease payments during the lease term should be associated with a reduction in the costs of obligations and interest, so that during the amortization period a periodic interest rate is obtained for the balance of the obligation.

The calculation of the current value of the minimum rent payments leads to the allocation of the percentage component of rent payments. The amount of interest is determined as the yield of the remaining amount of the rent obligation at the beginning of the period at the interest rate specified in the rent agreement, go to the tenant's internal borrowing rate (effective interest rate). The rate is discounted, equalizes the balance value of the asset or obligation and the amount of future cash receipts or payments, as a result of which the current balance value of the asset (obligation) on future cash flows is calculated.

The requirements of the international standard and account practice regulating the depreciation of fixed assets, including leased ones, were approached to the maximum.

It estimated in both account systems:

- The depreciable value of the enterprise must be regularly written off during the useful life of the enterprise;
- The current method of depreciation should reflect the process of consuming the economic benefits received by the organization from the asset;
- Depreciation charges for each period should be recognized as expense in the calculations and reports.

By concluding a financial rent agreement, the renter can cover the initial direct costs associated with obtaining subsequent financial income. Costs, such as commission, legal costs and other costs associated with direct negotiation and the formalization of the lease agreement, will reduce the initial cost of the receivable debt on financial rent and, accordingly, the amount of income that will be into account during the rent term. Thus, these costs distributed throughout the term of the rent based on the principle of the relationship between costs and income, and immediately not reflected as consumption. If the owner of the house is a manufacturer or dealer, the costs associated with negotiating and formalizing the rent agreement will be recognized as costs for starting the term of the lease immediately.

The financial income of the rent is subject to distribution over time on a systematic and rational basis, mainly according to the scheme reflecting the periodic rate of the outstanding amount of the principal debts of the rent. For the reporting period, the tenant's rental payments are calculated by reducing the principal amount of the debt, the financial income of the rental that has not been received

The financial income of the rental must be distributed to the unpaid amount of the principal debt of the rental, regularly reflecting the norm in a regular and justifiable manner. Since the principal amount of debts in the reporting period is less than the financial income of the rental, the rent payments of the tenant reduced.

Results and Discussion

The delay in the reform processes of the accounting system of the Republic of Uzbekistan during the development of the market economy led to the analysis of the results of the reform of the local accounting system. This study revealed that the methods of reforming the accounting and reporting system of the Republic of Uzbekistan and some elements of accounting in its internal

legislation are not disclosed today. In this regard, the following conclusions and the most important scientific results obtained in this study.

The main groups of problems of reforming the accounting system-economic, institutional as well as methodological and methodological. The problems of methodological and methodological nature are a central element of the set of interrelated problems, and the level of economic development of the country must be a deterrent factor in the construction of national standards to address the issue of balanced use of IFRS in national regulation.

It proved that the contradictions inherent in the reform of the accounting system as a whole and the Uzbek standards are the result of a group of problems of methodological-methodical character.

All proposed methodological approaches to the reform of the accounting system in accordance with IFRS are associated with the application of the method of step-by step adaptation of Uzbek standards to IFRS, which now requires revision. Methods of changing the national systems of accounting and reporting in the Republic of Uzbekistan and abroad – the methods of combining, standardization, harmonization and convergence of accounting systems were studied. To date, it been established that at the conceptual level there is no consensus among experts on what convergence (maximum convergence) of national standards with IFRS is and how it differs from convergence (gradual convergence) of Uzbek standards with IFRS.

With IFRS, barriers have been identified to reform the accounting system - specific characteristics of IFRS distinguish them from the internal accounting system: clear economic logic, the standards for the preparation of these reports (not accounting accounting), they have a structural feature in construction due to the hierarchy and integrity signs. In the IFRS system, the interconnectivity of standards and prints was justified.

The theoretical provisions necessary to eliminate obstacles to the convergence of the reform of the accounting system with IFRS - the differences between the domestic accounting system and IFRS substantiated. A set of Uzbek reporting principles identical to the principles of the IFRS system, which are the basis for the construction of Uzbek accounting standards, has been formed; the essence of the principle of "reliable presentation" of information in reporting and its place in the set of principles has been determined.

On basis of the existing regulatory documents, taking into account these proposals, a methodology was developed for the maximum approximation of Uzbek standards with IFRS: It is proved that the maximum approximation of Uzbek standards to IFRS in each period should be based on the initial degree of adaptation of the former to the latter.

It revealed that the indicator of approximation of Uzbek standards to IFRS is the degree of adaptation of Uzbek standards to IFRS, and the criteria for approximation of Uzbek standards. IFRS are the signs of hierarchy and integrity that determine the systematic construction of Uzbek standards.

Conclusion and Proposal

In the course of the study, the following summaries and suggestions were made:

One of the fundamental principles of rental accounting according to international standards is the predominance of the essence of the transaction over its legal form, which is fully realized when accounting for and reflecting lease agreements in the financial statements in the international financial reporting standard (IAS) 17 "Rental". In the work, the economic feasibility of reflecting the leased asset on the balance sheet of the economic owner was substantiated, a step-by-step transition to reflect financial rental transactions in rental reports has been identified.

In our opinion, allows us to systematize and concretize the accounting process, prepare financial statements in detail and thoroughly using the accounting data of rental transactions. The information contained in such financial statements becomes more useful for analyzing and making management decisions in the interests of the interested circle of users.

In the light of the changes taking place in the Republic of Uzbekistan in the field of accounting, there is a need to conduct a comparative analysis of the main provisions of the domestic and international procedure for reflecting asset rental transactions on accounting accounts. The purpose of such a comparison is to identify the main directions and significant discrepancies in the accounting rules, substantiate the current practice of reflecting rental transactions in the accounting of both systems and make a reasonable and balanced decision on borrowing international approaches to accounting for lease transactions in domestic accounting practice. Since the accounting

regulation of rental accounting operations in the Republic of Uzbekistan is not carried out by a single regulatory document, all domestic documents defining the procedure for accounting and reporting of rental transactions under financial rental agreements were reviewed and compared with the main provisions of international financial reporting standard (IAS) 17 "Rent".

In the course of the conducted research, the main directions identified in which there are significant differences in approaches to the reflection of rental transactions in accounting:

- This is the definition of the balance holder of the property;
- Methods of reflecting operations on accrual and recognition of rental payments and the absence of the concept of fair and discounted value in Uzbek regulatory documents.

The analysis of the two systems of accounting for rental transactions showed that in domestic and international practice, both approaches to determining the balance holder of property and options for assessing the value of such property differ significantly, which ultimately significantly affects the objectivity of the reporting indicators of the parties to the lease agreement.

As a result of the research conducted, the following suggestions were made.

The analysis of the approaches to the classification of types of Rental allowed to give an object an idea of the essence of the Rental agreement, therefore, in the future, to determine the method of accounting for lease transactions applied to a particular type of lease agreement. In this regard, within the framework of the study of the issues of accounting of rental relations, the main differences of international and local approaches to the classification of rental types in Accounting were analyzed, the main concepts accompanying the lease agreements were considered.

The proposed classification usually corresponds to the requirements of international standards and the existing internal system: regulation of rental relations. At the same time, one or another type of lease must be carried out in the form of a contract, based on the priority of the economic essence, taking into account the total amount of terms that accompany the transaction, and as a result of professional analysis and evaluation of all important terms of the contract. The implementation of this classification is a necessary condition for the approximation of rental operations within the framework of the internal accounting reform program in accordance with the IFRS, in particular, the

analysis of the content of the main normative documents regulating the accounting of rental operations showed the possibility and conditions for the application of the proposed approach in the conditions of.

In the course of the study, the conceptual framework of Rental accounting in accordance with international financial reporting standards examined and compared with the basic principles of the internal accounting system. Domestic rent accountancy accounting and comparison of printouts defined in the IFRS, it is possible to note their general compliance, although some differences are determined in certain rules, both in qualification and in practice. If some discrepancies in the quantification of accounting principles do not have a significant impact on the accounting reporting performance of an organization, in some cases inconsistencies in their practical implementation can have a significant impact on the reliability of accounting information.

In order to ensure uniform approaches to the practical implementation of accounting principles as part of the reform of the accounting system, it proposed to provide detailed instructions on the implementation of the basic accounting principles in regulatory documents of an explanatory nature based on the consideration of complex examples.

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MANAGING CONFLICTS IN VULNERABILITY AND PATCH MANAGEMENT FOR IT AND OT

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Abstract

All organisations need to manage vulnerabilities and a keyway to do that is to patch their assets. However, for critical infrastructure organisations that have Information Technology (IT) and Operational Technology (OT) devices and a strong focus on both safety and security ensuring those controls are implemented can be difficult. This paper will analysis the requirements of patching and vulnerability management and establish conflicts that can occur for IT and OT. A process to manage these conflicts will be created, including calculations to establish vulnerability and patch ratings. A case study will be used to show the controls being implemented. The paper concluded that conflicts and issues can be resolved and provided methods to resolve them. Often the conflicts are related to if a control goes wrong rather than a control that is implemented correctly causing a conflict. The process created will allow critical infrastructure organisations to implement the required controls without impacting safety and security.

Keywords: Vulnerability management, patch management, safety, security, IT, OT

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Introduction

Often organisations look to balance Information Technology (IT) security risks with the need for the organisation to operate its core business. Whereas organisations that manage critical infrastructure need to also balance safety risks and Operational Technology (OT) risks.

Safety, security, IT and OT have similarities and differences, by understanding the similarities and differences organisations will be able to better select controls and manage conflicts between the two areas. Safety and security should not be treated in isolation (Lisova et al., 2019) and will be more effective when controls are applied taking both into consideration.

Two control areas where this can be seen is vulnerability management and patch management. Critical Infrastructure (CI) organisations have safety and security standards they may follow or comply with and the standards especially security will require these two control areas to be implemented.

Vulnerability management is looking to detect and reduce vulnerabilities. One way to do this is via patch management which is focused on applying code known as patches to software used by the CI organisation. The number of vulnerabilities and patches continue to raise (Furnell, 2016) which adds more pressure for organisation's to manage the vulnerabilities and patches promptly as the risk is increasing.

Problem and Novelty of Solution

The main problems this paper is going to resolve are IT and OT are managed and configured differently (Homeland Security, 2016) which means the security controls that are applied to IT can conflict with safety objectives and cause issues for OT. It can be difficult to implement the controls and comply with safety and security standards (Kanamaru, 2020) as they have different aims and objectives.

This aim of this paper is to propose a process that will work for both IT and OT while maintaining both safety and security. To create this process the paper will highlight conflicts and issues and ways to resolve those issues. Another solution to the problems will be to use calculations to establish the OT vulnerability risk rating and the patch assessment rating which will establish how critical the patch is and the impact on the organisation of patching.

There are processes that describe how to create a vulnerability and patch management process (National Institute of Standards and Technology, 2013), but they are designed for standard organisation's and not CI organisation's. Even when a process does consider CI it does not resolve many of the conflicts that IT and OT have and usually just recommends the same controls are applied on IT and OT. This is often not possible or could impact the operation of the CI organization.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows section 2 will discuss the differences between safety, security, IT and OT. Section 3 will introduce the case study that is used to show the controls being implemented. Then section 4 will explain the controls for vulnerability and patch management. The conflicts and issues and how to resolve them will be presented in section 5. Section 6 will present two calculations that have been created to help assess vulnerability and patch management. The final section in the paper is section 7 the conclusion.

Differences with Safety, Security, IT and OT

Safety and Security

ISO 2700 - Information security management systems (International Organization for Standardization, 2017) defines security as “preservation of confidentiality, integrity and availability of information” while IEC 61508 Functional safety of electrical/electronic/ programmable electronic safety-related systems (International Electrotechnical Commission, 2010) define safety as “freedom from unacceptable risk” they are both quite high level statements but in general safety is usually seen as protecting people from harm while security is seen as protecting data the organisation has.

Safety has in the past been seen to focus on accidental risks while security on intentional risks (Kriaa et al., 2015) but that has begun to change. Intentional risks can also cause a safety incident such as a malicious user purposely opening a flood gate. Also, accidental risks such as a flood can impact security’s aim to preserve the availability of data, so that difference is now much smaller with them both having more in common.

Often safety risks were considered equipment failure or natural hazards which although are still the case many other threats that are more security related are now in scope of safety risks. Such as data manipulation, or remote access being gained to the safety systems. From a security perspective security risks were considered external threats. However, now they can also be internal and equipment failure and natural hazards are threats that security teams also need to manage. This shows that differences in the past are now beginning to be less significant with the current way CI organisations are operating.

A difference that also impacts the way safety and security interacts is that they are managed by separate teams who often take a different view and approach to the areas they manage. This can make it more difficult when both areas are converging more and ensuring an efficient way of working is achieved.

As IT, OT and the components that CI organisations require become more integrated this also brings safety and security closer together as security incidents can now lead to safety incidents which is another reason both areas need to be managed in a more integrated manner.

Vulnerability and patch management will need to be applied to different parts of the CI organisation such as IT, OT, buildings and components such as sensors and valves as a few examples. A large amount of the controls will be aimed at IT and OT so it is important to describe what each one is and the differences they have as by understanding the differences the CI organisation should be able to better understand how to apply the controls to both.

IT and OT

Both terms are overarching terms and within them there are other terms that are used to describe the components that make up IT and OT. For example, in IT terms such as servers, networks and applications are used and within OT some examples can be Supervisory Control and Data Acquisition (SCADA), Human-Machine Interface (HMI) and Programmable Logic Controller (PLC). Within each of the other terms it can be more detailed such as a financial applications or PLC for a sensor etc.

(Kriaa et al., 2015) mentioned that safety and security were two distinct fields, but they are beginning to converge more and will continue to do so and the same can be said for IT and OT. IT systems were used as business tools for activities such as spreadsheets, communication and file storage as examples. While OT were separate and used to manage industrial operations such as physical equipment including valves and pipelines these systems were very different and were often separate from the IT systems (National Institute of Standards and Technology, 2015). For many reasons including efficiency and cost OT systems are being connected to the Internet and beginning to use IT systems such as connecting with laptops which have USB and standard operating systems installed. This has advantages but also disadvantages as the risks that IT systems faced are now being faced by OT systems (Holcomb, 2015). However, as will be described they are not designed to operate in the same way and for that reason cannot always use the same controls in the same manner to manage those risks. Compared to OT (Conklin, 2016) highlights, IT systems have over the years been designed with more security inbuilt or security controls have been created to help protect the IT systems and the information they contain the same cannot

be said for OT. The focus on OT was to ensure it was reliable and available when needed to help ensure safety of the components it managed and overall safety of the CI organisation. Due to the way OT was setup security especially Internet based risks were not seen as a major concern. However, as IT and OT converge security is now becoming much more important for OT.

A difference between IT and OT is the lifespan of the technology, OT is expected to have a much longer lifespan it can be over 20 years while IT is usually much shorter such as around 5 years (Owl, 2019). Even though IT systems have a shorter lifespan they have updates applied throughout that time to help them stay secure and resolve vulnerabilities that were not known at the time of release. OT does not apply the same principal on updates to their systems as there is a strong focus on not impacting availability which an update could have. However, security risks can also impact availability, so this difference needs to be overcome.

It does depend on the what the task is for the IT system but in general the monitoring and response of an OT system will be more time sensitive (Bimco, 2020) due to the nature of what it is controlling. An alert on a file server could be reviewed within 24 hours while an alert on a pressure sensor will need to be reviewed almost instantly.

IT systems are more open and have better integration with other IT systems while OT systems tend to use proprietary systems that do not always integrate well with other OT or IT systems. This can mean different OT systems have to be supported by different users and vendors.

Resources is another place IT and OT differ. IT systems can have their resources increased more easily and have enough resources for controls such as anti-virus software to be installed on them. Whereas OT it is not as easy to add resources (National Institute of Standards and Technology, 2015) and, they tend to be created with the necessary resources to do their task and not have extra resources for controls such as antivirus software.

It was mentioned OT systems are focused on safety and IT systems are more focused on security due to this many of the current security controls cannot always be applied to both systems. For example vulnerability scanning takes place on IT but is not as common in OT for fear of impacting the running of the OT systems. Network protocols for IT systems are common and well known while OT are niche and may not be understood by the current network security tools on the market. OT systems connect with physical real-world devices such

as sensors and gates while IT systems do not usually manage those devices. This difference can be seen in the strong need for safety controls on OT but not as much in IT systems.

As the previous few sections have shown it will not always be possible to take the IT security controls and place them on the OT systems to make them secure. The differences in the two areas mean that at times this will not be likely and other solutions will be required. Also, the differences between safety and security can cause issues with the implementation of safety and security controls and will require further work.

Case Study

A case study has been created to highlight how controls can be applied and how conflicts can be identified and resolved within the case study.

An electricity company called East London Power (ELP) has a dam and hydroelectric power station in Essex and provides electricity to the local area. They employ 200 people and are based in two locations the first is the location of the dam and hydroelectric power station which is on the River Lea and the other is their office location which is based in East London. They also utilise outsourced support companies.

The company is divided in to three different areas:

- Dam and power station - Area of responsibility is the maintenance of the dam and power station and the production of the electricity.
- Commercial – This part of the business manages the selling of the electricity and handles all account management.

resources to do their task and not have extra resources for controls such as antivirus software.

It was mentioned OT systems are focused on safety and IT systems are more focused on security due to this many of the current security controls cannot always be applied to both systems. For example vulnerability scanning takes place on IT but is not as common in OT for fear of impacting the running of the OT systems. Network protocols for IT systems are common and well known while OT are niche and may not be understood by the current network security tools on the market. OT systems connect with physical real-world devices such as sensors and gates while IT systems do not usually manage those devices. This difference can be seen in the strong need for safety controls on OT but not as much in IT systems.

As the previous few sections have shown it will not always be possible to take the IT security controls and place them on the OT systems to make them secure. The differences in the two areas mean that at times this will not be likely and other solutions will be required. Also, the differences between safety and security can cause issues with the implementation of safety and security controls and will require further work.

Case Study

A case study has been created to highlight how controls can be applied and how conflicts can be identified and resolved within the case study.

An electricity company called East London Power (ELP) has a dam and hydroelectric power station in Essex and provides electricity to the local area. They employ 200 people and are based in two locations the first is the location of the dam and hydroelectric power station which is on the River Lea and the other is their office location which is based in East London. They also utilise outsourced support companies.

The company is divided in to three different areas:

- Dam and power station - Area of responsibility is the maintenance of the dam and power station and the production of the electricity.
- Commercial – This part of the business manages the selling of the electricity and handles all account management

Figure 1 - ELP Network Layout

Vulnerability and Patch Management Controls

This section will list the main controls and then use the case study to show how the controls can be implemented and where conflicts can arise. **Error! Reference source not found.** gives a brief description of the control. Control areas often overlap and some controls from another area may be needed for the vulnerability and patch management controls to operate correctly these controls will be highlighted as supporting controls but will not be covered in detail here.

Table 1 - Vulnerability and Patch Management Controls

Control	Description
Asset inventory	A complete asset inventory is required so that the CI organisation knows what assets it has to patch and check for vulnerabilities. This is a control area in its own right and is more a supporting control for this section.
Monitor vulnerability sources	Vendors such as Microsoft, Abode and organisation's such as CVE and NVD release information about vulnerabilities that are discovered. CI organisation's should monitor these sources for information and check them against their systems to see if they are vulnerable.
Vulnerability scans	One of the main controls within vulnerability management is using a vulnerability scanning tool to scan the assets and look for vulnerabilities.
Vulnerability assessments	This can be other types of assessments were vulnerabilities can be identified such as during architectural reviews, lessons learned from incidents, audits and during project planning.
Penetration testing	This is a more advance and intrusive form of assessment. The penetration test will look to exploit the vulnerabilities and the testers will behavior in the same manner an attacker would to look for vulnerabilities in the systems.
Code analysis	If the code for the application is available this can be analysed and vulnerabilities identified.
Patch assessment	This will involve assessing if the patch is required, the criticality of the patch and what systems require it as examples.
Sourcing patches	Before the CI organisation can apply patches, it needs to gather the patches from the appropriate sources. This involves locating and securely receiving the patches.
Patch testing	Before patches are applied to all the production systems it should be tested to ensure it will not impact the systems. Testing should be done on a selection of systems.
Apply patches	One of the main controls of patch management is deploying the patches. This can be via an automated process or manually applying patches to the systems. The patch management configuration is also managed when applying patches.
Verify installation of patches	As potentially thousands of patches will be applied to the systems the CI organisation needs a way to verify the patches have been installed correctly.
Control governance	This is a generic term that captures all the governance tasks around the control such as reporting, establishing the team, metrics and providing remediation tasks to the relevant teams.

This list is just a brief description of each control and each control will have much more details and implementation options that the CI organisation must decide on. Standards such as ISO 27002- Security techniques — Code of practice for information security controls (International Organization for Standardization, 2013), NIST 800-40 Guide to Enterprise Patch Management Technologies (National Institute of Standards and Technology, 2013), and NERC CIP-010-2 - Cyber Security — Configuration Change Management and Vulnerability Assessments (North American Electric Reliability Corporation , 2016) can provide further information on the controls if required. What follows now is a few more details on certain key controls listed in Error! Reference source not found.

The first step is to understand what assets ELP has and identify if they are in scope for vulnerability and patch assessments. ELP has separated out their business into three distinct areas; dam and power station, commercial and support each area has assets that are in scope and selected. The commercial and support areas only have IT assets and have a strong focus on security while the dam and power station section have IT and OT assets and are concerned with safety and security.

A key part of the vulnerability management process is conducting vulnerability scans on the assets. ELP have decided to use a third-party vulnerability scanning appliance and to use a hybrid-cloud approach. The team selected this approach as it reduces the costs and still provides a good level of security. The commercial and support areas of the business will use the cloud version of the vulnerability scanning appliance which is cheaper than having an appliance on site while the dam and power station area will have an appliance onsite scanning the assets within that area. The team decided on this set up as it reduces the external connections into the dam and power station network and also keeps the information from the vulnerability scans internal to the network.

The team will look to use all controls in combination where it can, as this is better than just using one control such as vulnerability scanning only. Penetration testing and code analysis can identify other vulnerabilities that vulnerability scanning would not. Once ELP has identified the patches required for its assets, it needs to assess which patches to install and when. To assess the patches the team will need to consider the following points and from the point of view of installing and not installing the patch.

- Safety
- Security
- Productivity
- Downtime
- Threats
- Vulnerabilities
- Hazards

There are more but this should help the team focus on the main areas, and they are all related such as threats are part of safety and security for example. To help ELP assess their patches, a calculation (Equation 1-1) has been created that is used to give a patch assessment rating for each asset/patch combination. Section 6

Vulnerability and Patch Assessment **Calculations** describes the formula in detail.

A key part of the patch management process is applying the patches on the assets. ELP have decided to use a third-party patch management appliance to help apply the patches, the patching appliance is installed on a server in the head office and is located on the support network area. The patches will either be applied automatically or manually. If the patch is being deployed automatically then the third-party patch management appliance will be used and for the manual deployment the patching team will work with each asset owner and deploy the patches on each asset individually.

The assets that are receiving the patches automatically are located in all three areas of ELP which are commercial, support and the dam and power station. However, it will only be the IT assets in those areas that get them automatically the OT assets within the dam and power station will get them manually.

The patch management process that ELP has created, is designed to assess the risks of patching and not-patching on assets and provide the details needed to carry out the patching. It was mentioned that conflicts and issues can occur in the process between safety and security and between the different types of assets such as OT and IT. Also, problems can arise when patches cannot be applied or cause issues with the assets. The next two sections will focus on these conflicts and issues and provide guidance on what the CI organisation can do to resolve them.

Conflicts and Issue Resolution

The previous section described the controls that CI organisation's can use. This section will now analyses the conflicts that can occur and provide solutions that can be put in place.

Sourcing Vulnerabilities and Patches

Vulnerability and patching sources for OT is not as easy compared to IT. OT vendors do not publish as much detail on their vulnerabilities and in some cases the OT is so old the vendor is no longer providing patches and is unlikely to even be looking for vulnerabilities. The lack of vulnerability sources can mean it is harder to find details on vulnerabilities which in turn makes it harder to detect vulnerabilities within the OT systems.

Some potential solutions to this issue are to use the same vulnerability information that is used for IT as some may be applicable to OT as well. The CI organisation can directly approach vendors if patches do not appear to be available and enquire if and when they will be available. The OT manual can be used to find default settings that may be enabled which can be a vulnerability such as default passwords being used. Another control is to keep a record of when patches were last applied, if it is a long-time, patches may have been missed and should be inspected. Making vendors contractually required to provide patches if possible can be a good way to ensure they continue to provide patches. The CI organisation should build a strong relationship with other CI organisation's so they can share vulnerability and patching information that could impact them both. Other controls such as penetration testing and code analysis can provide vulnerability details. A final control if a vulnerability scan cannot be run on a device would be to use an asset management tool to find software versions and missing patches that way instead.

Sourcing Patches

Not all vendors will consider patching important and may not provide a good level of security around the patches and that can make it difficult for the patch management team to securely source the patches.

If that is the case the following methods can help. The CI organisation should contact the vendor for a secure transfer method instead of downloading from their website. They should analyse the code of the patch to see if there is anything malicious or that looks out of place. The patch should be installed in a

sandboxed environment at first to monitor the patch activity and ensure it is as expected. Also, the file size should be checked and scanned for viruses.

Vulnerability Scanning Configuration

The vulnerability scanning configuration for IT will not be the most appropriate configuration for OT and can have conflicting areas. For that reason, the following configuration settings should be made for each area to reduce conflicts and issues.

The vulnerability scans for IT will be carried out monthly while OT scans will be quarterly. IT scans will take place overnight, while OT will depend on water levels and electricity demand and take place when the assets are less utilized. The IT scans will have no users involved and run on their own automatically. Whereas the OT scans have the following users involved:

- Vulnerability team – Monitoring the scan
- OT asset owner – In case of issue with the asset
- Safety and security team – To provide support if needed
- Vendor – On call for support if needed
- Dam and power station users – If issue with asset occurs can complete tasks manually while asset is unavailable

When the vulnerability scans take place, it is likely IT assets may have a backup system as part of other controls. For OT, if there is no backup system in place, the team should be onsite to manually do the job of the asset in case there is an issue and the asset is not available. A final difference is all IP addresses are scanned for IT devices, while only selected IP addresses will be scanned for OT.

Patch Testing

The main conflict for testing is the requirement that patches are tested before they are applied to the assets. There may be times when the patch cannot be tested first as it is only going on the one asset and there are no backup or spare assets for the test to be applied to.

There are several controls that can be put in place to resolve conflicts in patch testing. These are to use a patch assessment rating to understand the impact if the patch goes wrong and an assessment is created in section 6 for this use. That can help the team understand how much of a risk they are taking by patching without testing. The CI organisation could see if other organisation's have had

issues with the patch. To reduce the risk of applying a patch that has not been tested, owners of connected devices should test their device is not impacted and be onsite in case of issues.

Penetration Testing

Penetration testing can impact assets and an issue can occur if no backup or non-production version of the asset is available. To resolve those issues and lower the risk the following controls can be used.

The team carrying out the penetration testing should ensure the owners of the assets backup the data on the live systems before the test is conducted. An appropriate time that would cause minimum issues if the test negatively impacts the asset should be selected. In advance the asset owner should document how to carry out the process of the asset manually incase that is required. High risk tests such as Denial of Service (DoS) will not be carried out. Another option if possible is to use virtual assets for the penetration test instead of the live systems. However, the virtual asset should be an accurate representation of the production system.

Applying Patches

There are many conflicts with trying to apply patches in the same way for IT and OT. The conflicts and ways to resolve them are described in this section.

Some patches cannot work on the patching appliance and instead of being installed on the asset via the appliance will need to be done manually. The CI organisation should patch IT and OT at different times to reduce the risk of issues occurring on both at the same time. Within OT the team should consider whether to stagger the patches or do them at the same time for all devices. Staggering can reduce the risk of multiple devices being impacted at the same time but will require multiple downtimes for the CI organisation. The force reboot that is applied for IT patches should be disabled for OT patches with the asset owners being able to choose when is an appropriate time to reboot. This should be tracked to ensure it does take place.

Separate patching appliances can be setup in different network areas such as one for IT and OT. If there is only one patching appliance for all areas extra security controls should be implemented and care should be taken to ensure the different configuration settings for IT and OT are not mixed up and applied to the wrong areas. Another control is for the backup team to backup the asset

before the patching takes place so an up to date backup is ready if needed. An outage could occur at the CI organisation for various reasons and the patching team could take advantage of the fact the devices are not in use and carry out the patching and required reboots at the same time. A potential problem with this control is that depending on what is the cause of the outage it may not be the best time to also carry out patching while the teams are dealing with an outage and the outage could be resolved before the patching finishes. A final control is if the patch is released but is not available for the current version of the asset the team can reverse engineer the patch to see what it is for and then attempt to manually resolve the issue on the asset if applicable.

Verify Patches

Verifying patches for IT can be done via the patch management appliance but as OT is done manually that may not be possible. For this reason, it can be difficult to verify manual patches compared to IT.

The CI organisation should consider the following options. Setting up Security Information and Event Management (SIEM) logging on the OT assets, ensuring any patch related logs are sent to the SIEM which can then report on the patch status. A different approach can be to scan the OT with an asset management tool to see if patches are installed. Also, before applying next month's patches the team can manually check the previous month's patches were applied and installed correctly.

Not Applying Patches

There will be times when a patch cannot be installed or is installed and has to be removed and when this happens other controls are needed. ELP uses a defense in depth approach to safety and security and do not rely on one control only. This means when the control of patching cannot be applied other controls will be used instead to reduce the overall risk.

Some example compensating controls are to increase logging and monitoring, to capture suspicious activity. The team should investigate the ability to upgrade the asset to a newer version. A newer version should be able to be patched. File integrity monitoring can be implemented on the asset to detect changes to files which can be a sign of compromise. Another compensating control is to set up an Intrusion Detection Systems (IDS) both host based, and network based to monitor traffic and actions. If possible remote access should be removed from

the asset, so the only way to access the device is in person physical access. The asset owner should disable certain features on the application that are not critical to reduce the attack service. Also, if the patch relates to a specific service look to disable that service or feature so it cannot be exploited. The CI organisation should isolate the system from other devices. This will make it more difficult to access to compromise and can reduce impact if compromised. Also, increasing user awareness so that users look out for suspicious activities. The controls and activities that have been described in this section are designed to reduce the risks of conflicts or remove the conflicts and allow ELP to still carry out the vulnerability and patch management controls. The controls chosen will be dependent on the risk appetite of the CI organisation and the conflict that is occurring.

Vulnerability and Patch Assessment Calculations

Establishing what the risk of a vulnerability is or how a patch will impact an asset are often difficult to quantify. CI organisation's will have a risk management process which can help but this paper has created calculations specifically aimed at vulnerability and patch management.

Patch Assessment Rating

The patch assessment rating will establish how critical the patch is and the impact on the organisation of patching. Other papers have created patch calculations such as (Shariffdeen, et al., 2020) which created a calculation to apply patches to similar programs and (Wang et al., 2020) where patch correctness was calculated. These were used to help establish what should be considered in this paper's calculation.

For the patch assessment rating, the formula for the calculation is made up of several parts. The first part of the formula is Asset Value (AV) the team will need to understand and assign a value to the asset that is being patched. The AV can be a value between 1-10 with the higher the number the higher value the asset is. It should be noted that value here is not referring to a purely financial value. The next part of the formula is the Safety Impact (SI) this is the safety impact the patch will have on the asset. The team need to consider will the patch improve the safety of the asset. Such as will it add more stability to the asset, or a new feature. Often patches are a preventative measure so will not improve safety and

are more security focused. The team will give a value of 1-5 with the higher the number the more it will improve safety.

Security Impact (SecI) is similar to the Safety Impact but is based on security. The team will consider how the patch can improve the security of the asset. For example, are their known exploits that are in use for this vulnerability, can the vulnerability be exploited remotely and how difficult is the exploit to do. A major aim of patches are to resolve vulnerabilities and improve security so when the team are deciding on a the SecI they need to consider how big the security risk is that the patch applies to. Patches can also introduce security vulnerabilities even though it resolves one and that should also be considered when assigning a value. The team will give a value of 1-5 with the higher the number the more it will improve security.

The Productivity Impact (PI) part of the calculation is considering the impact the patch will have on the productivity of the asset and the overall organization. For example, will the asset need to reboot for the patch to install, will it remove some features of the software or slow the software or hardware down. The productivity of the asset could improve with the patch being installed, it may resolve issues that caused the software to crash or run slow or add new features that make users more efficient for example. The team need to assess all these issues and provide a value of between 1-5 with the higher the number the more of a positive impact the patch will have.

As with anything there is a risk that applying the patch could have a negative impact on the asset and/or organisation. This is what the Negative Impact (NI) value is focused on. The team need to look at what could go wrong with the patch such as if the asset is no longer able to perform the function that it is designed for, or it has become more unstable and crashes or has a degraded performance. What would be the impact of the CI organisation if that was the case. The team will consider what would be the consequences of an issue with the patch and give a value of between 1-5 with a higher value meaning a bigger impact would be possible. Error! Reference source not found. provides a description of each Negative Impact value between 1-5.

Table 2 - Negative Impact Value provides a description for each value.

Negative Impact Value	Description
1	If the patch goes wrong, it will have a very minor impact on the CI organisation
2	If the patch goes wrong, it will have a minor impact on the CI organisation
3	If the patch goes wrong, it will have a reasonable impact on the CI organisation
4	If the patch goes wrong, it will have a considerable impact on the CI organisation
5	If the patch goes wrong, it will have a major impact on the CI organisation

Negative Impact Value Description

- 1 If the patch goes wrong, it will have a very minor impact on the CI organisation
- 2 If the patch goes wrong, it will have a minor impact on the CI organisation
- 3 If the patch goes wrong, it will have a reasonable impact on the CI organisation
- 4 If the patch goes wrong, it will have a considerable impact on the CI organisation
- 5 If the patch goes wrong, it will have a major impact on the CI organisation

Table 2 - Negative Impact Value

To establish how critical the patch is and what impact it will have on the CI organisation the following calculation is used:

$$PV = AV + SI + SecI + PI \quad \text{Equation. 1-1}$$

Where PV is the Patch Value. Error! Reference source not found. shows what ELP has decided the patch assessment ratings will equal for the patch value and the details of how the patch assessment ratings can impact patching will be discussed later. A higher patch assessment rating will show the patch has the potential to have a large positive impact on the asset\CI organisation.

Patch Assessment Rating Patch Value

High More than or equal to 16

Medium More than or equal to 8 and equal to or less than 15

Low Equal to or less than 7.

Table 3 - Patch Assessment Rating

Patch Assessment Rating	Patch Value
High	More than or equal to 16
Medium	More than or equal to 8 and equal to or less than 15
Low	Equal to or less than 7.

As there is a risk when applying patches, the team also want to understand how that risk is balanced with the need to apply the patch. That is what the Negative Impact (NI) value that was given earlier is used for, Table 2 - Negative Impact Value shows the description for each value and the team will compare the patch assessment rating and the NI value. There is no set rule for what ELP will do when a certain patch assessment rating and negative impact value are selected for the asset it is just a guide to help the team gain a better understanding of the value the patch will bring and the potential impact if it goes wrong.

The patch assessment process considers many different things as this process is covering both safety and security so it requires assessing areas which may not be considered if it was just patching purely from a security perspective and not looking at both safety and security. The assessment will not be required for every single asset, the team will be able to group similar assets and conduct one assessment for them all. For example, all laptops within the commercial area can use the one assessment rating.

The patch assessment calculation is designed to not only give a value and a rating to the patches and assets but also it makes the users think about safety, security, issues and the assets themselves. This is important as the patches can have a range of positive and negative consequences which the users will consider as they work though the assessment and calculate patch assessment ratings.

OT Vulnerability Risk Rating

To help the CI organisation establish what the potential risk could be to the OT from vulnerability management a calculation has been created which the team can use to rate the risk for each asset. The calculation looks at the controls and OT differences compared to IT and potential solutions. Previous papers have created

vulnerability risk calculations such as (Singh& Joshi, 2016) that created a model to estimate the security risk level of the vulnerability. While (Hong et al., 2014) used the Attack Representation Model (ARM) and included Importance Measures (IMs) to calculate what to patch. These papers helped to understand concepts needed for creating a vulnerability risk calculation such as the one used in this paper. The calculation and formulas are described next

Vulnerability Inherent Risk rating (VIRr) is the overall rating for the risk of vulnerability management on the asset before any conflict and issue solutions are applied. That rating is made up of the following figures:

Vulnerability Sources rating (VSr) – This is a rating of between 1 -5 for how well vulnerability sources are currently available for the asset not including the conflict and issues solutions. The higher the number the less resources are available.

Scanner Settings rating (SSr) - This is a rating of between 1 -5 for how well the CI organisation can separate IT and OT and use different scanners and scan settings. The higher the number means the appliances and settings are more likely to be the same for IT and OT.

Penetration Test rating (PTr) – This is either a rating of 1 or 5 and it represents if the asset has a backup system that can be used for the penetration test instead of the production system. The rating of 1 is for yes and 5 is for no.

To summarise $VIRr = VSr + SSr + PTr$

The Vulnerability Rating risk percentage (VRrp) is the overall percentage that the conflict and issue solutions will help reduce the risk of vulnerability management on the asset. The rating is made up of the following figures:

Each rating is taken from Error! Reference source not found.. It can be seen that even with all solutions used the risk is only reduced 30% this is because the solutions cannot ensure the issues will not occur.

Table 4 - Vulnerability Rating risk percentage

Reduction Rating	Description
5%	Very few of the solutions can be used
15%	Some of the solutions can be used
30%	All the solutions can be used

Vulnerability Sourcing Solutions (VSS) – Table 4 is used to select the description and rating that best suits the solutions that can be applied to that asset for vulnerability sourcing.

Scanner Settings Solutions (SSS) - Table 4 is used to select the description and rating that best suits the solutions that can be applied to that asset for the scanner solutions.

Penetration Test Solution (PTS) - Table 4 is used to select the description and rating that best suits the solutions that can be applied to that asset penetration solutions.

To summarise $VRrp = VSS + SSS + PTS$

N is the sum of the calculation of VIRr and VRrp.

Operational Technology Risk (OTr) – is the overall OT risk score of using vulnerability management on the asset. The higher the number the higher the risk is, each CI organisation can decide on their risk appetite and what level of risk they can have.

The formal calculation for the OT risk is:

$$(VIRr \div 100) \times VRrp = N$$

$$VIRr - N = OTr$$

These calculations can provide ratings for assets and allow CI organisation's to prioritize vulnerabilities and patches and also identify which are the higher risk and will require more controls.

Conclusion

A key aim of this paper was looking for conflicts in safety and security as well as within IT and OT. The controls that vulnerability management includes should improve safety and security. The main risk is around availability and if an asset becomes unavailable that could impact safety but that could impact security as well. The issues only occur if the control goes wrong rather than a control that is implemented correctly having a conflict with safety.

There can be various remediation activities depending on the vulnerability and they could cause safety conflicts or could have issues working on both IT and OT. It is important to understand remediation work from vulnerability management may in itself cause conflicts and issues and even more than the vulnerability management controls themselves. The team can use the vulnerability management calculation to help them prioritize the vulnerability findings and provide a risk rating for them.

The patch assessment calculation will help the CI organisation establish several important pieces of information including:

Asset value

Will it improve safety and security

What impact will it have on productivity

What are the consequences if the patch goes wrong
 What happens if the patch is not applied

Overall patch assessment rating

All of this information is used throughout the patch management process to help decide what other actions are required and how each patch and asset will be managed. The patch assessment phase has the potential during the assessment to identify conflicts and/or issues. For example, the assessment could highlight that an asset requires a patch but has no way for the patch to be tested before deployment. The Conflict and Issue Resolution section provided guidance that can be used when the patch assessment identifies those issues.

It is important to note that the conflicts and issues that are being discussed in this paper can apply to OT and IT. Often OT are the assets that have these issues but IT assets can also have conflicts and issues that means a patch cannot be applied or a server has no backup and requires high uptime but requires a reboot. The controls here can also be used for IT and OT, the key is to assess each asset\patch and calculate the risk and controls required to reduce that risk.

If patches are not applied this can impact security and safety. Often patches are aimed at a security vulnerability so not patching will be a security risk. However, it can also be a safety risk as if that device is compromised due to the missing patch a malicious user could take control of the connected assets such as the spillway gate and cause a flood which will be a safety issue. There is also the conflict that by applying the patch to improve security it could cause an issue with the asset which then impacts safety, the controls and issue resolution section has provided guidance on how to lessen that risk and resolve the conflict.

This paper has shown controls that can be applied for vulnerability and patch management and used a case study to demonstrate the controls being implemented. The conflicts and issues that could occur and ways to reduce those conflicts or lessen the risk of a safety or security incident were given.

The calculations that were presented can be used to help identify the level of risk involved and then the CI organisation can decide if more controls are needed to

reduce the conflict or if the control will not be implemented at all and other compensating controls will be used instead.

Safety and security are very important for CI organisation's and with IT and OT playing a key part in both. Organisation's need to manage conflicts that can occur and find ways to implement controls while ensuring safety and/or security are not compromised.

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EFFECTS OF CRUDE OIL CONTAMINATION ON ATTERBERG LIMITS OF SELECTED SOIL ON THE SOUTH WEST KIRKUK-NE IRAQ

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Abstract

The aim of this study is search the effects of adding crude oil on the atterberg limits of fine grain soil samples selected on the south west Kirkuk –NE Iraq. Due to the lack of information about this crucial topic in Iraq and in particular in Kirkuk city which is one of the richest oil cities in the world, this topic has been selected. The engineering properties of the study samples included (water content, grain size distribution, specific gravity and Atterberg limits). According to USCS the sample is (ML). The study sample was divided into two parts. The first part is uncontaminated soil (0%) which carried out for Atterberg limits tests, the second part is sub-divided into (four portions) crude oil was added to the four portions as (2%, 4%, 6%, 8%) after placing the contaminated samples in sealed containers for a period of two weeks (to gain sufficient homogeneity) then the Atterberg limits tests were carried out for those contaminated samples. The results indicated that increasing the percentage of crude oil from (0% to 4%) due to an increase in the Atterberg limits, and this may be attributed to the fact that the increase in the addition of crude oil to fine soil may lead to a distortion of the internal structure of clay minerals, after an increase in the percentage of crude oil (6% and 8%), a decrease in the values of (Atterberg limits) occurred as the doubled increase in crude oil leads to the replacement of a layer of non-polarized crude oil for liquids instead of a layer of water that surrounds the clay granules, which constrains the access of water to the fine particles.

Keywords: Atterberg limits, Kirkuk city, crude oil, engineering properties of soil, oil contaminate .

Introduction

Oil leaks usually occur during transportation, which leads to the difficulty of removing contaminated areas. There are several sources of oil pollution, such as the breakdown of transportation pipelines, accidents of oil tankers, marine oil

products [1]. The impact of oil spills is no longer only a adverse impact on the earth's ecosystem, while its impact has exceeded the safety of engineering projects as well as the leakage of hydrocarbon fluids occurs through the movement of these fluids to the bottom of the earth, due to the gravitational effect of semi-saturated soils, access to the groundwater levels [2]. After 2003 war, Iraq, especially the oil-producing areas, witnessed many environmental accidents related to oil leakage from tanker pipelines or oil tanks, as a result of terrorist operations that led to the leakage of huge quantities of oil into the soil, surface water and groundwater (Figure. 1). These oil leaks are certainly it negatively affected on the environment, including changing the engineering properties of the soil, and that was a justification for this study.

Figure (1): forms of oil pollution in Iraq (1) and (2) oil pollution in the study area (new oil processing plant- SW of Kirkuk) (3) oil pipeline explosion in southern Qayyarah/Mosul 2016 (<https://www.unep.org/ar/alakhbar-walqs>) (4) pipeline explosion in Kirkuk (Bay Hassan field) (<https://www.aljazeera.net/news/politics> 2021).

There are many among the researchers who studied the effect of adding crude oil on the engineering properties of the soil, such as [3], who studied the effect of crude oil pollution on the index properties, strength and permeability of clay loam soil, where it was found that the Atterberg limits of the soil increased with the increase in the addition of crude oil, while there was a decrease in the values of specific gravity, permeability and upper dry density. [4] observed that the destruction of the fine atomic structure of the clay after adding diesel oil to it

under the scanning electron microscope (SEM), while investigate the effect of the leakage of diesel oil to the soil in the city of Mashhad (western Iran) noted by [5]. decrease in the ability of the soil to bear the loads with oil pollution of the soil. In addition above many searches were working out in this topic like [6] [7]. due to the fact that the city of kirkuk is an oil city, and there have been many crude oil leaks in all its forms as a result of sabotage operations that led to the pollution of large areas of the soil in addition to its contamination of surface water, and because not touched for this type of topic among researchers and academics in the city of kirkuk was all justification for choice this search. Our study aims to investigate the effect of adding crude oil to the soil taken from (a site close to the north oil company in kirkuk) on the properties of the atterberg limits different percentage of additions of crude oil.

The Location of the Study Area

The study area is located near the (new oil processes plant that is part of the north oil company (NOC)), which is about (17 km) southwest of the city center of kirkuk - NE iraq and within the coordinates of (N35°24`10`` - E44°12`53``) Figure () (2). The study area is covered with modern sediments represented by varying amounts of clay, sand, silt and gravel, in addition to the presence of a seasonal river stream (chai su) that is exploited as a gravel quarry in the region. at the same time, there was a clear soil contamination of the site through the crude oil coming out of the new oil processes plant. The area is part of an unstable within the foothill zone according to [8].

Figure (2) : location of study area

Materials and Methodolgy

About (30 kg) Undisturbed soil sample was taken from the study area at depth about (20 cm) below the surface of the earth to avoid the surface layer. A small amount of soil was placed in an airtight container to measure its moisture in the laboratory, while the rest was transferred to the laboratory after being placed in storage bags. Before the samples were dried at room temperature, water content measured based on [9] and then specific gravity measured according to [10] in the engineering geology laboratory at the college of science/university of kirkuk. While the test of grain size distribution of the soil, it was conducted in the laboratories of the (Kirkuk construction lab.) by dry and wet methods, according to [11].

Soil sample divided into two parts, first part a (non-contaminated) samples with crude oil (0%) which tested for Atterberg limits , the (second part) was subdivided into (four parts), crude oil has been added to the four parts as (2 %, 4%, 6%, 8%). After placing the contaminated samples in airtight containers for a period of two weeks (to gain sufficient homogeneity) (Figure () 3)

Figure (3) : (A,B) stages of preparing contaminated samples.

After obtaining homogeneous soil with crude oil at percentages (2%,4%,6%,8%), all samples were subjected to (Atterberg limit test) in the (Kirkuk construction lab) according to American standards (ASTHO T89 and T90)

After obtaining the liquidity limit values, plasticity limit and the plastic index for contaminated samples the results were compared and discussed.

Results and Discussion

Uncontaminated Sample : Table (1) and Figure () (4) showed that the soil sample in this study includes (gravel 1%, sand 32%, silt 50% and clay 17%) , while the values of the Atterberg limits of fluidity, plasticity and plasticity index are (24.55%, 10,05% , 50,14%) respectively and according to the standard soil classification USCS the soil sample can be classified as silty sandy soil (ML) reflects an environment with polygenetic source [8]. it is noted from the table that the water content value is 6.5% and the specific density is 2.65.

Table 1: physical properties of uncontaminated sample

Soil properties	values
Grain size distribution	
gravel	% 1
sand	% 32
silt	% 50
clay	% 17
Specific gravity	2.65
Water content	% 6.5
Liquid limit, w_L	24.55
plastic limit, w_P	10.05
Plasticity index, I_P	14.50

Figure () 4: Grain size distribution of sample

Contaminated Soil Analysis Results

when observing the results of the Atterberg limits analysis by adding different percentages of crude oil, there are changes in the engineering properties of the soil that occurred with the increase in the addition of crude oil table (2) Figure (5) the increase in the proportion of crude oil from (0% to 4%) leads to a clear increase in the (liquid limit LL, plasticity limit PL and plasticity index PI) this may be attributed to the fact that the increased addition of crude oil to the fine soil may lead to a distortion of the internal structure of the clay minerals, which leads to the

Table 2: Results of Atterberg limits value of contaminated soil sample.

Atterberg limits	0%	2%	4%	6%	8%
Liquid limit	24.55	26.11	26.37	26.83	24.53
Plastic limit	10.05	18.74	22.94	19.74	21.34
Plastic index	14.50	7.37	3.43	7.08	3.19

Figure (5) : Atterberg limits results of contaminated soil sample.

Expansion of the inner layers of those minerals and thus to the difficulty of working and forming those clays [3] . After that, an increase in the percentage of crude oil (6% and 8%) will result in a decrease in the values of (LL,PL,PI) these results were similar to the results of [6] and [7], as the doubled increase in crude oil leads to the replacement of a layer of non-polarized crude oil for liquids instead of a layer of water that surrounds the clay granules, which hinders the access of water to the fine granules.

Conclusions

In this study, the soil sample can be classified as silty sandy, low-plastic soil that reflects a sedimentary environment of multiple origins. The addition of crude oil to the soil at rates of (2,4,6,8%) affects the properties of the Atterberg limits, as there is a clear that increase in the values of the liquid limit and the plasticity limit when adding crude oil at rates of (2%,4) due to the change in the fine internal structure of the clays, which lead to the expansion of the inner layers of these minerals, and thus to the difficulty of working and forming those clays, while for percentages (6% and 8%), there is a decrease in the values of the liquid limit and the plasticity limit, due to replacing a layer of non-polarized crude oil for liquids instead of the water layer that surrounds the clay granules, which impedes the water's access to the fine granules.

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IN CATTLE – A METHOD OF TREATING NODULAR DERMATITIS

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Annotation

This article describes a number of effective methods currently used to detect and treat nodular (nodular) dermatitis in cattle.

Keywords: 4,5 thousand, European countries, CJuneipoxvirus, Nitox 200.

Relevance of the Topic:

nodular dermatitis is an infectious – viral disease that is accompanied by swelling of the connective tissues and organs of the skin. It affects the skin, the lymphatic system, mucous membranes, eyes, and becomes numb with tuberculosis in tissues. Nodular dermatitis disease is currently considered to be common in cattle. This disease is considered infectious and is observed in such cases as constant urge to urinate, swelling of the skin, serous-mucous discharge in the nose, lack of appetite. According to official data, in the Republic of Chechnya more than 4,5 thousand cattle infected with nodular dermatitis are registered.

According to information, the cassette was vomiting in all regions and districts in the south of the country. Due to the lack of vaccines against cutaneous at that time, the Prevention of nodular dermatitis has not been brought. Nodular dermatitis appeared for the first time in Chechnya in August 2015 year. This disease was penetrated from Dogistan and Azerbaijan. At first, this disease was considered relatively rare, and later this disease spread to the regions of the south of the country. It was found that kasalik was distributed by blood-sucking insects.

This disease is registered mainly in Central and South Africa, Madagascar, India, later in the Middle East, Turkey, Lebanon, Iraq, Iran, Egypt, Russia, Dogan in 2014-2016 years

Nodular dermatitis is a viral infectious disease caused by the causative agent of the CJuneipoxvirus breed.

contact with animal;

- Through insect bites;

- * Contact with products of slaughter of sick animals or their biological fluids;
- * Fertilized equipment;
- * Contaminated feed;
- Sex between animals.

Etiology. Cytopathogen effects and viruses that are distributed in three groups of cattle animals, cytopathogen effects that are distinguished by cytopathogen effects, allerton (alletrton) and nitling (nething). Viruses of Nitling Group are the main pathogens of nodular dermatitis of cattle.

Symptoms of nodular dermatitis in large cattle are similar to symptoms of thrush,

but there is no such obvious difference in its stages. After 5-6 days, when infected, seals appear, similar to tuberculosis of the skin. Around each of them there is inflammation of the skin, the diameter of the tumor can reach 20 cm, at this time there is an increase in the body temperature of the animal, weakness, thirst. With a complex course of musculature,

muscle tissue is involved in this process.

Symptoms of nodular dermatitis in cattle with large horns:

- * Hyperthermia-an increase in body temperature by more than 40 degrees;
- Runny nose, lacrimation;
- Formation of dense tubercles up to 0,5 cm in height and up to 7 cm in diameter;
- In the center of the knot, hair falls out and a necratic process begins;
- After 7-20 days, the affected areas dry up and the crust disappears from them;
- * Enlarged lymph nodes;
- Ulcers appear on the mucous membranes;
- * Formation of complete or partial blindness;

Dyspnea, difficulty breathing, abundant salivation, mucous or mucous - purulent conjunctivitis, blurred vision of the eye membrane, enlargement of the lymph nodes are possible, in accordance with the passage of the stool, digestion of food, increased pain and injury of the joints.

Methods of Treatment

To prevent the disease, nodular dermatitis of cattle is vaccinated every year. This event gives imunitet for 1 year. And calves can be vaccinated in 2 months. After injection, 10% of animals show a nodule or swelling that disappears by itself

within 2 weeks. Only timely vaccination will prevent pet cramps with nodular dermatitis.

Infected animals are separated or destroyed, which prevents the epidermis. In livestock houses, deforestation measures are mandatory. Sick animals are thrown into a diet enriched with vitamins.

Most of the livestock is restored independently. Symptomatic treatment, of course, is prescribed by a veterinarian.

Nitox 200

Treatment of nodular dermatitis:

1. Nitox 200-according to the instructions.
2. Bitsilin 5 - 3 million pieces, in 4 days.
3. Tetravit-5 ml per week.
4. Creolin-bathing procedure is carried out every 3-4 day.

Nodules are prescribed in severe forms of dermatitis, for 1 Week additionally 2 liters of rosehip and sodium chloride. 5ml of caffeine can also be sent under the skin. Some people afsal treat their pet by traditional methods, with which veterinarians do not interpret it. It is forbidden to eat milk and meat of sick animals. If the cow has died of nodular dermatitis, then its body needs to activate. Dermatitis is an infectious disease, mainly affecting the skin of cows. In cattle, dermatitis occurs as a result of contact with a sick animal, but is transmitted by infectious agents, clothes of peasants, blood-sucking insects, or birds. Treatment of cows with nodular dermatitis depends on the onset of the disease and in what condition the cattle are in.

Nodular dermatitis

Also nodular dermatitis in a cow can appear after a person is removed from the veterinary register. Due to this feature, the spread of infection can occur at different times in the herd and in different people.

Nodular dermatitis can not be detected immediately, because the first symptoms, if they are noticeable, are a few days after the infection. Most often, itching on the skin of cattle appears a week after the infection, but the reference book indicates the presence of nodular dermatitis, which is manifested in the period from 2 days to 45 days, so the detection of such symptoms during such a period of time is indicated. The acute stage of the disease is mainly a derivative for young animals.

When the first signs of the disease appear in cows, this is reported to the veterinarian. It is not necessary to appoint an independent diagnosis and treatment, there are many diseases that have similar symptoms. The final diagnosis is made when taking samples from blood and skin, and after examining these samples in the laboratory.

If nodular dermatitis is confirmed, it is worth starting a course of treatment. If the virus has infected the entire body of the cow and quickly spreads to other representatives of the cattle, euthanasia is required to prevent suffering and stress, as well as to prevent the spread of infection to other animals. In addition, the farm is disinfected, and the products (milk, meat and skin, etc.) are destroyed on a reliable scale.

Treatment of dermatitis of nodules in cattle involves the use of certain drugs. There is no special treatment for this type of dermatitis, therefore, a common drug with a very effective effect against skin diseases is used. Usually treatment is complicated by several medications. To increase the dose and prevent death, it is necessary to follow the instructions.

Treatment of dermatitis in cows varies depending on the age of the animals.

Young cattle

Treatment of dermatitis in calves involves the use of vaccines and drugs in small doses. There are two common types of treatment Kompleks, among which three drugs are used.

The First Option:

- RIBAVEX – injected under the skin in a dose of 1ml /10 kg per body weight once a day for 5 days;
- MULTIVET is a drug that is administered once in a dose of 2-6 ml/10 kg intramuscularly.

Ribavex is effective in the treatment of cattle bacterial and viral diseases.

The second option:

- COMBIVET-intramuscularly injected 2 times a day from 5 ml 2 times a day to 10 times the body weight;
- Uber – a drug that is injected intramuscularly, 5 times a day;

- MULTIVET is a drug that is intramuscularly administered once in a dose of 2-6 ml/ 100 kg.

Uber normalizes the processes of metabolism and recovery, increases resistance to negative ecological factors and stresses, promotes the reproduction and development of cows.

Kata for the treatment of senile cattle, the same drugs, in comparison with young animals, are used only in large doses.

Conclusion

Nodular dermatitis of cattle is an infectious disease caused by a virus, characterized by short - term Isthmus in the subcutaneous tissue and their necrosis, skin lesions, lymphatic system, mucous membranes.

For the first time this disease was observed in Rhodesia in 1929-th year, clinical symptoms were described in 1931 - th year. Later, it began to spread to countries such as South Africa, Madagascar and India.

The mortality rate in this disease does not exceed 10%. However, the economic damage is on the floor, because of milk and meat productivity, the quality of skin raw materials decreases, in cows the sexual silk breaks, and in Bulls temporary infertility develops.

When the cattle are restored, quarantine is removed from the farm and appropriate control work is carried out, the meat of the cattle will be suitable for human consumption, since the virus mainly affects the skin and the tissue layer of the meat. In addition, the virus of nodular dermatitis is not contagious for people.

Although nodular dermatitis has existed since the 90s in old age, this disease has not been studied much in European countries. It is very difficult to solve this and leads to huge economic losses.

PEDAGOGY OF TEACHING IN NATIONAL MUSICAL ART

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Annotation

This article is regarding the improvement of imaginative capacities of future educators, the rudiments of instructive abilities in proficient schools, the preparation of future instructors in the single man's framework, the expert advancement of future instructors. The characteristics and elements of preparing are portrayed.

Keywords: future teacher, staff training, pedagogy, creative ability, continuing education, pedagogical skills.

Introduction

Man has showed up, there is a course of childhood, instructive action has been happening since the start of childhood. The calling of instructing and childhood is a respectable and profoundly capable, troublesome and complex calling in every single social framework. In free Uzbekistan, the change of the procedure for proceeding with instruction, the redesign of the instructive interaction based on new instructive norms, unique consideration is paid to the exercises of instructors, their educational abilities.

As the primary President said: "We are dealing with an earnest issue, for example, giving teachers present day information, working on their insight and abilities. As I would like to think, this is the fundamental issue in changing the schooling system. We request that the educator give our youngsters current information. In any case, to give present day information, as a matter of first importance, the mentor should have such information. "

The continuous fruitful execution of the public preparation program in our nation generally relies upon crafted by instructors, expanding their expert notoriety. Hence, the childhood of a sound, balanced age relies upon the level, preparation and commitment of the educator working in the means of proceeding with training, his mentality to crafted by instructing and teaching the more youthful age. The educator satisfies the social mission of the general public, so in the

preparation of exceptionally qualified trained professionals, the instructor should meet certain socio-political, academic and individual necessities. Subsequently, the instructor has a confidence in the possibility of independence, a very much evolved logical reasoning, proficient information, ie a profound information regarding the matter, an expert of academic correspondence, educational mental and strategic information and abilities. have the option to rapidly see, study and assess different academic circumstances. Should have the option to pick the most proper techniques and method for instructive impact.

Raising a sound age, which is the eventual fate of free Uzbekistan, is a fragile, incredibly requesting, inside struggle process. Thusly, the course of arrangement of the instructor, the understudy and the student ought to be seen with incredible energy and care. He should have academic information and abilities while driving the instructive cycle. Really at that time would the educator be able to dominate the pith and persuasion of educational peculiarities, the strategy for academic work, calling and innovation and expert instructive abilities.

Everybody's capacities and gifts are answerable for improvement. An individual's capacity relies upon their natural capacity, contingent upon the climate, on the instruction the individual in question gets, as well as an individual's capacity in view of their inborn capacity, contingent upon the climate, on the schooling the person gets. It develops and develops because of its work on However, it ought to be borne at the top of the priority list that the impact of the climate alone isn't enough for the development and improvement of ability. The main thing is instruction and extraordinary childhood.

An educator with instructive information and abilities should initially know the strategic reinforcements of teaching method, the regulations and elements of self-awareness, the pith, objectives and targets of the public preparation program. Numerous teachers working in the schooling system have a profound comprehension of the need and significance of instructive abilities during the time spent training and childhood.

Along these lines, they are continually endeavoring to work on their abilities, get current information and involvement with agreement with the high necessities of today, to work innovatively. Notwithstanding, it should be recognized that a few instructors in instructive establishments don't feel the significance of working on their academic abilities and are not keen on concentrating on the prerequisites of the Law on Education, the National Training Program. , hastily take a gander at the logical idea of the instructive cycle, its pertinence to present day prerequisites, its

association with life and practice, don't continuously recollect the logical and philosophical instructive solidarity of the disciplines educated. This is because of the way that the degree of information and abilities of the understudies they study is lacking, they fall behind in dominating the educational program.

With regards to instructing and instructing the more youthful age during the time spent carrying out the procedure for proceeding with training, this exceptionally intricate and diverse errand can be done simply by qualified educators. In this way, educating is an incredible workmanship. Either educator can only with significant effort and unexpectedly accomplish this workmanship. To do this, the instructing calling, that is to say, the longing of a solid age to turn into a genuine mentor, has an extraordinary energy, rapidly and profoundly gets the prerequisites of the times, reliably executes its logical, socio-political level, educational abilities. , can be accomplished simply by evident nationalists and diligent employees, very much equipped with the thought and philosophy of autonomy.

Academic ability is anything but an inborn ability or a characteristic passed down from one age to another, yet a result of examination and inventive work. At the core of this multi-layered instructive movement lies imaginative work. Accordingly, instructive abilities are not a norm for all educators, or at least, a standard approach to working, yet it is framed and created during the time spent self-study, imaginative work of every instructor.

In this interaction, the instructive abilities and experience of a high level instructor ought to be contemplated by another educator, utilized innovatively and improved by cutting edge insight. The academic abilities of the educator are apparent for the most part in the study hall, in the homeroom. Along these lines, it ought to be logical, philosophical and famous, and ought to be related with the degree of arrangement of understudies.

During the time spent schooling, it is fundamental for the educator and the understudies to have an exuberant language, correspondence, true demeanor, regard, participation in accomplishing the principle objective. Shallow, viable experience, isolated from life, comprising of general words and dry admonishments, shallow proper talks and different examples are not important to understudies, they are not intrigued by logical examination. , philosophically lacking nourishment. Accordingly, it is important to arrange the preparation so that under its impact understudies have various perspectives, logical reasoning and convictions in this subject.

The more noteworthy the effect of the course of schooling and childhood, as a matter of first importance, on the logical capability of the educator, his standing among youngsters, individual characteristics, logical ability, experience and abilities in the field of training and the association with understudies. It relies upon the laid out amicable mentality.

In his discourse at the initial function of the Academy of State and Social Construction, the primary top of our state I.Karimov said:

"An individual who instructs and instructs somebody, most importantly, should be balanced in all regards." The necessities of the time are that teachers and educators ought not be restricted to the information and even out they have, however ought to tirelessly and determinedly concentrate on the experience of far off nations, burrow profound and afterward show their understudies. kidladi.

The viability of educational movement likewise relies upon how much the educator's academic capacity is debilitated. Teacher M. Ochilov noticed that the capacity is made and created during the time spent movement, and suggests the accompanying kinds of educating capacities. These incorporate the capacity to know, the capacity to clarify, the capacity to notice, the capacity to talk, the capacity to acquire renown, the capacity to convey.

Educational capacities and abilities are not handily framed in an educator. To accomplish this objective, an individual who picks this calling must continually study, study and examination, work imaginatively, straightaway get the real factors of our free nation and profoundly feel the significance of their work for the country.

While pondering the educational abilities of an educator, it is important to focus on his cognizance, dedication to the public thought and philosophy, the broadness of information and thoughts, his demeanor to his assignment. Specifically, it is important to consider the requirement for a wide scope of thoughts of the instructor in educational abilities. Since, supposing that an individual doesn't have wonderful information and thoughts, he can not accomplish flawlessness. Truth be told, one can take care of either issue through thought. Thusly, an individual seeking to get instructive abilities, obviously, should continually grow their insight, update the understudy, the thoughts and contemplations that ethically affect the understudy. To do this, he should concentrate on a great deal. In surveying the instructive abilities of an instructor, it is critical that he can sort out schooling. Ideal association of examples and talks in proceeding with instruction is the main undertaking of the instructor. Themes covered at a general will stay in

the personalities of youngsters for quite a while, will successfully affect the development of their confidence, convictions and philosophies. Subsequently, the logical level of the instructor is reflected in the mentality to their obligations, the craving to mentor youngsters, academic abilities, basically in examples and talks. The degree of appraisal of a science educator's movement still up in the air by the nature of the example and talk.

As well as being a method for inside and out information, the educator's preparation in the specialty of instructing, as well as the improvement of free Uzbekistan, trust from here on out, the insight and difficult work of our kin, fills in as a reflection of what should be done to become a commendable resident and manufacturer.

Allow our childhood to be happy with the examples of their mentors. Allow them to stir heartfelt dreams, foster reasoning, pragmatic movement, innovative capacities, want to study and work. Allow them to feel that they have obtained information and abilities, got otherworldly sustenance, not with the grades they got after the preparation. Significant, fascinating and justifiable training fortifies the essence of the educator and understudies, reinforces earnest regard and common trust between them. To do this, the educator should initially dominate his subject and strategies for showing it, the significant degree of instructor mentor culture, regard and love for their understudies, interest in their lives and temperament. information and understanding, smoothness, capacity to control feelings, appearance, regard for the way of life of dress, significant degree of discourse culture, movement in open issues, particularly among the public logical instructive and profound ought to be advertisers of social undertakings. Really at that time will our understudies, who are the eventual fate of our nation, name their mentors with extraordinary regard and profound appreciation. To do this, each educator should have an applicable information regarding their matter, high expert preparation and high upright person, as determined in the Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan on Education.

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CHARACTERISTICS OF RESPECT FOR ADULTS IN ELEMENTARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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ANNOTATION

The article contends that the arrangement of components of regard in play, work and communication with peers in understudies will fill in as an establishment for them to be adequately capable in their next, progressively complex age.

Keywords: Sense (inllect), manners of behavior, humanistic interrelation, human qualities

Introduction

The idea of "regard for grown-ups" is a wide one. The idea of "regard" additionally contrasts as far as the bearing and nature of the exercises did by the individual.

"Regard" is a moral class of profound quality, which portrays the demeanor of the person to society, the sign of high private and moral characteristics to meet his necessities. The obligation of the individual is appeared in his mentality to the entire being, to the singular demeanor to every particular circumstance.

In Higher Education (Dictionary-Reference), this idea is deciphered as understanding and controlling one's own conduct: "Regard is a type of self-government, self-acknowledgment. practices and their results, as well as their capacity to comprehend and control their own current circumstance and characters. " In our perspective, regard isn't a type of self-legislature of an individual, yet rather his conduct and demeanor to other people, which obtains the personality of independence and sociality. There is additionally a lexical blunder in the given definition. The Uzbek language doesn't have the sentences "comprehend and control one's capacities in the climate" and "comprehend and control one's capacities in the climate." For this situation, the creators allude to

"society" or "social being", "currently friendly relations"; It would be proper to utilize ideas, for example, "exclusively".

Understudies are instructed that "regard for grown-ups is a crude character characteristic. At this age, this characteristic is just shaped. It lacks the opportunity to turn into a firm conviction. Regard for grown-ups in perusing turns out to be more imitative. The way that youngsters recognize grown-ups in perusing isn't on the grounds that they get the social and individual significance of perusing, but since the requests of guardians and instructors are that way. Albeit the obligation of play in grade school understudies has settled somewhat, it is prudent to lay out academic management in its further reinforcing. Thusly, while involving instructive and instructive games in the study hall and outside the homeroom, the educator should ensure that understudies approach each other with deference.

The way that elementary school understudies have the characteristics of regard for grown-ups will assist them with settling on a mindful way to deal with work, including learning. In this manner, it is a stage towards teachers' desired objective to underscore to understudies prior to beginning the game, that they really must get a sense of ownership with the undertakings appointed to them. It is additionally great to accomplish the objectives and goals of the game however much as could reasonably be expected, to draw the consideration of the members, to urge them to pursue the end-product.

It is a new, significant bearing of every day exercises of elementary school understudies. Work in the essential grades is coordinated to guarantee that understudies get fundamental socially helpful work abilities. In elementary school, socially helpful work is coordinated as class shifts. Understudies are engaged with study hall exercises, for example, cleaning work areas and work areas and seats, and setting up the board for the following illustration or next work out. Socially valuable work guarantees that study halls are spotless and clean and illustrations are smooth.

The association of class shifts is particularly significant in the arrangement of regard for grown-ups in grade school understudies. All things considered, obligation forces specific undertakings on understudies, yet additionally helps them to approach this interaction in a serious way.

The educator ought to consistently screen the exercises of understudies during the association of the shift, to expand the consideration of understudies to the ideal end of errors made by them, to screen the conduct of understudies who

can coordinate the obligation at a significant level. verbal excitement and assessment make them need to view the interaction more in a serious way. The development of a capable way to deal with learning exercises assumes a significant part in the arrangement of regard for grown-ups through the association of work exercises for elementary school understudies. Thusly, perusing is the fundamental type of action of elementary school understudies. "A mindful mentality to perusing is a functioning, successful disposition. It is difficult to concentrate on it with information and substantial outcomes in instruction, persistence, self-analysis, industriousness. Obligation is joined with the requirement for understudies to procure autonomous information, to apply it imaginatively by and by, to continually grow and extend information.

Regard for grown-ups by grade school understudies makes the reason for the development of such characteristics as freedom, mindfulness, the capacity to accurately survey various circumstances, which are significant necessities for the characteristics of a cutting edge individual. Along these lines, "... the attention on the development of drive, obligation and autonomy in the youngster should be really important in the beginning phases of tutoring. The fundamental type of sign of these characteristics at a youthful school age is instructive autonomy.

As referenced, every understudy is an individual from a specific class. In this manner, he should play out specific obligations to his group, have the option to consider the necessities of the group. Generally in grade school the accompanying prerequisites are set for every understudy by the class group:

- 1) Ideal participation;
- 2) Not to miss classes without an explanation;
- 3) Be perfect and efficient;
- 4) Perform class shifts as an individual from the group;
- 5) Pay attention to the guidelines of instructors;
- 6) Coexist with cohorts;
- 7) Helping cohorts when important (for instance, getting data from debilitated schoolmates, assisting them with concentrating on points in different subjects);
- 8) Dynamic support in different rivalries with the group;
- 9) Customary interest in extracurricular or extracurricular exercises;
- 10) Principled execution of the obligations allocated to him as a class obligation official;

- 11) Help with preparing the homeroom (for instance, brightening the study hall with houseplants);
- 12) To add to the assets gathered for the maintenance of the homeroom or school working under the support of guardians;
- 13) Facilitate a full class or school parent meeting (class pioneers normally illuminate guardians about the class or school parent meeting. The opportune conveyance of the message to the guardians extraordinarily affects the nature of the gathering. Consequently, the ideal conveyance of the message to the guardians of the understudy is before his group. Implies the satisfaction of obligation).

Essential classes outfit understudies with innate sciences, for example, "The World Around Us" and "Inherent Science", as well as "Perusing", "Manners" and "Constitution Lessons". As understudies become familiar with the guidelines of managing the climate and nature, they understand the requirement for a dependable way to deal with this interaction. Therefore, the disposition of grade school understudies to the climate and nature is likewise significant in the improvement of regard for grown-ups.

Mental and academic lessons stress the significance of work in the development of the person for quite a long time. All things considered, work guarantees the development of an individual actually and physiologically, yet additionally profoundly. During the time spent work, an individual's awareness creates, his reasoning grows and his perspective enhances. Through work, an individual fosters an uplifting perspective towards others. As per present day mental methodologies, the disposition to work and work action makes the accompanying two circumstances: 1) the adequacy of work is guaranteed; 2) the individual has a chance to accomplish specific triumphs and accomplishments. Simultaneously, work assembles trust in one's own assets and capacities. It is vital to utilize the instructive effect of work, to include the elementary school in different socially helpful exercises. It is likewise a unique instructive assignment to shape the qualities of regard for grown-ups in grade school understudies based on the potential outcomes of instructive disciplines and otherworldly instructive exercises.

Broad social endeavors are being made to resolve the issue of human wellbeing and insurance, avoidance of different irresistible infections at the degree of all-inclusive issues. The principal prerequisite of human wellbeing is to fortify the obligation of every individual for the security of individual wellbeing. In such

manner, it is prudent to foster individual wellbeing abilities in elementary school understudies through the instructing of scholarly subjects and the association of a progression of otherworldly and instructive exercises outside the study hall. Accomplishing that elementary teachers regard grown-ups for individual wellbeing shows that academic movement is coordinated successfully.

Guardians are expected to be the nearest consultants and advisers for the elementary school understudy in regarding grown-ups and playing out their obligations. As needs be, the foundations of the essential schooling system ought to have the option to lay out solid binds with families and arrange joint exercises. This implies that instructive foundations, yet additionally guardians, ie families, should be engaged with the development of regard for grown-ups in grade school understudies. As section 1.2 of the thesis accommodates an extraordinary conversation on the collaboration of families and instructive organizations in the arrangement of regard for grown-ups in grade school understudies, it is worth focusing on here. We accept that teeth are excessive.

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SKILLS OF CREATIVITY IN MAKING DOLLS

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Annotation

The article analyzes the repair, reconstruction and rational use of buildings and structures.

Keywords: Reconstruction, operational indicators, technical inspection, moral obsolescence, physical obsolescence, conservation, modernization, overhaul, restoration, technical re-equipment, expansion of existing enterprises, repair, strengthening of structures.

Introduction

During the years of independence, unprecedented work has been done in the field of reconstruction of buildings and structures. In particular, the Main Department Store in Tashkent - Chorsu Shopping Center, Alpomish Sports Palace - Exhibition Hall, Construction Technical School - Institute of Chemical Technology, Children's World Store, Tashkent Hotel, Turkestan Hotel and others. The Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the First President of the Republic I.A. Hundreds of magnificent lyceums and colleges, thousands of secondary schools have been reconstructed and brought up to modern standards by implementing a number of Karimov's decrees (1,2,3). Many sports facilities have been reconstructed and built, especially for the development of children's sports.

Reconstruction and technical re-equipment will significantly reduce capital expenditures compared to new construction and cover costs 2-2.5 times faster. Reconstruction has played an invaluable role in improving the appearance and unique appearance of our cities. In particular, during the years of independence, the unrecognizable change in the appearance of our city was due to the large-scale reconstruction and modernization work. Landscaping and landscaping works are being carried out on a large scale. Reconstruction has a complex character and should be carried out taking into account the long-term prospects

of the city, region, enterprise. Otherwise, only the work done today will create a number of difficulties in meeting the needs of future reconstruction.

This complexity is important not only from a technical and architectural point of view, but also from an economic point of view. Reconstruction of residential, public and industrial buildings is usually carried out in conditions of high density. This does not allow the use of a complete set of construction machinery and equipment, the organization of storage space to create a standard stock of 5 materials and items. The existing dimensions of the crossings can also be very difficult to bring to the structure (especially large ones). There are also serious difficulties in locating load-bearing mechanisms for convenient installation in the assembly area. In the case of removal or installation of structures, sometimes the use of cranes is not possible at all, and it is necessary to look for a simpler design solution to the problem. A number of proposals are being developed and implemented for such cases, based on the use of both traditional and new solutions, constructions made of high-strength materials.

Reconstruction of buildings and structures is associated with the restoration and strengthening of the performance of load-bearing columns. This work, in each case, requires a different approach than the new construction. It should be noted that the assessment of the technical condition of buildings and structures, the conclusion that they need to be repaired or strengthened, as well as their suitability for further operation, is based only on the technical inspection of a particular object. It is important to monitor the condition of existing buildings and structures during operation. An example is a comprehensive study conducted for more than 15 years at the Ostankino Tower of the Moscow Television and Radio Center. This research includes the study of the deformation of the foundation, the work of the tower concrete, the observation of the stretched wire ropes, the study of the vibration parameters of the structure.

The experience of researching the radio and television tower built in Almaty is also of particular interest. The work was comprehensive and began with a study of its model. For the first time, a tower with a base of 18.5 m and a height of 372 m was built in a mountainous area with high seismicity.

The mass of the metal structure used in this case is about 5,000 tons. At present, the quality control service for the manufacture and installation of building structures in the country is not sufficiently organized. In particular, regular inspections of the condition of unique buildings and structures in operation,

prevention of possible adverse events (uneven drowning, various injuries and defects, etc.), or take the necessary measures during the start-up. This will extend their service life and leave them in good condition for future generations. In this regard, the relevant ministries, local governments register existing architectural monuments, unique buildings and structures, introduce a document (passport) with technical specifications for each of them and study the technical condition over time, ie monitoring. 'specializes in transmission it would be expedient to conclude economic contracts with research and project organizations. There is no denying that this event is extremely important in view of the fact that the variety and volume of transport has increased significantly, the impact of anthropogenic factors has increased, and in conjunction with natural disasters such as earthquakes and strong winds.

Great experience has been gained in all major cities of the country in the reconstruction and modernization of old buildings. Especially in the capital Tashkent, the work done during the years of independence is enormous and provides sufficient scientific and technical opportunities for large-scale research. In this regard, the materials presented to you in this brochure mainly reflect the experience of reconstruction work in Tashkent.

During the reconstruction, it is necessary to solve the engineering and technical tasks based on the level of spiritual or physical deterioration of the buildings. Spiritual obsolescence occurs as a result of volumetric, structural solutions or functional obsolescence of the building's engineering equipment, or all three classifications together do not meet modern requirements and the growing demands of people, ie the price of the building at the time of construction (apartments, hospital wards, laboratories, etc.).

The last decade has seen a significant shift in the pace of urban housing construction. 95% of the work on standardized projects must be carried out in strict compliance with the requirements of regulatory documents. Some relative changes in housing design standards (1957, 1962, 1971, 1985, 1989) have made it possible to create houses of different generations of standardized design. Physical wear and tear is the result of a decrease in the initial technical properties of the structural elements of the building during use (strength, durability, insulation ability, etc.).

As mentioned above, the obsolescence of a building and its structural elements means the deterioration of their technical condition, which reduces their cost. Based on the analysis of the results of inspections of building renovations, the

type of technical measures for renovation, such as capital repairs, modernization or reconstruction, is selected: Technical measures for the preservation of architectural monuments are based on their conservation (protection) or reconstruction. Overhaul means the elimination of physical deterioration of structures, the restoration of engineering equipment improving the physical and technical properties (strength, fire resistance, heat, sound and water insulation) and replacing equipment without changing the design or architectural solutions of buildings.

Modernization

In addition to the complex work carried out on the overhaul, in addition to the work on the interior redesign of the building, in some cases, radical changes are carried out without changing its size and appearance.

Reconstruction is the most complex form of reconstruction of a building, which involves the restoration and improvement of quality of structures, replacement of engineering equipment, redesign, in some cases the size of the building (adjoining building, construction, reduction of floors, etc.) and its external is to change its appearance.

Preservation (Preservation, Preservation) –

A set of technical measures to protect and strengthen the existing form of architecture without altering (even partially) the appearance or interior of architectural monuments.

Restoration of Monuments - (Unlike Conservation)

Is the only way to protect monuments from damage, allowing them to make certain changes or additions to the object being restored, which are necessary for its preservation and use.

The purpose of the reconstruction is to update the historical and architectural-compositional solutions of buildings by means of renovation-preservation, reconstruction, complete reconstruction, improvement of urban environments and others. Reconstruction of existing enterprises with the reconstruction of existing workshops and service facilities, as a rule, without expanding the main premises, changing the nomenclature of products and improving capacity, quality and production. and increase its technical and economic level based on the achievements of the ITJ (scientific and technical process) and improve their

working conditions and protect the environment, mainly without increasing the number of workers.

Technical re-equipment of existing enterprises - introduction of advanced equipment and technologies in some productions, shops and sections, mechanization and automation of production, modernization and replacement of obsolete equipment, including physically obsolete equipment, their technical and economic complex measures to raise the level of education.

The goal is to accelerate production, increase production capacity, improve quality, increase labor productivity, save material and fuel and energy resources, and more.

Expansion of Existing Enterprises

the construction of new shops and additional production, as well as the expansion of existing separate shops of main and auxiliary production in order to create additional production capacity on the territory of existing enterprises or their adjacent areas.

Repair of structures is the restoration of their operational characteristics and classification by eliminating one-sided deviations, defects and distortions.

Reconstruction of a structural element is a change in the design or layout of a building frame (barrier) due to changes in technical re-equipment requirements and operating conditions.

Technical condition is a set of features of a structure, including its protection against compliance with standards and conditions, fire resistance, heat, sound, noise insulation, etc...

- 1) Satisfaction - the building meets the requirements of operating conditions and standards without repair, reinforcement or reconstruction;
- 2) changes that require repair or reconstruction to meet the requirements of standard operating conditions and standards;
- 3) unserviceability - it is not technically possible or economically feasible to restore the operational classification of the structure and it is necessary to replace some elements, sections (parts) of the building or all the structures of the carcass.

Reinforcement

Aimed at increasing the load-bearing capacity of the structure as a whole or some of its elements (heat, sound, etc.)

a set of measures.

Structural reliability is the probability that a structure will operate without damage during its normal service life.

Standard service life is the period specified by the standards, during which the structures must meet the operating conditions and requirements.

Natural Confirmation of Structures

A way to compare the design of structures, steps, signs, lengths and shears of elements, dimensions and location of fasteners (welds, bolts, fasteners, etc.), the nature of determining the size, location of defects and failure of elements. measuring with. Structural inspection is an inspection of the structure of a building or structure in order to obtain information about the technical condition of the structures required for the development of the project of repair, strengthening or reconstruction.

Conclusion

Measures taken to partially or completely change the functional function of buildings and structures, to install new efficient engineering equipment, to beautify the territory of the building, to bring it into line with the high standards of the time are called reconstruction. It will be part of a complex of industrial enterprises, urban areas, housing estates, social and cultural institutions. Redevelopment includes redevelopment, increasing the height of the rooms, partial separation and replacement of structures, as well as the upgrade, implementation of adjacent devices and preference for the facade of the building.

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